

Chapter 2

A Security-Aware Governance Framework

1. Selecting a Framework for Modeling the Governance and Management of Security

In, this section, we compare the state of the art methods involving the conceptual modeling of security in order to select the most relevant framework to base ourselves on in the context of this research. We used google scholar to find these frameworks and narrowed the research by selecting frameworks that focus on Business IT Alignment (BITA) and that are goal-oriented or/and industry-adopted. The keywords used search for the frameworks include *service-driven modelling, business-IT alignment, model-driven engineering, goal-oriented social modelling* or *security modelling*. We compared the found frameworks on the basis of six criteria. These criteria have been selected because we want to build a framework based on conceptual models allowing to position security elements (i) at multiple levels and (ii) within the entire organizational context affected by and IT service's adoption. These criteria are:

- **Service-driven** refers to the delimitation of a software system's entities into coarse-grained elements called services [1]. The latter do have a seamless and tightly integrated interaction [2]. Services are well suited elements for IT governance on one side [3] but also for forward engineering (i.e. transformation) and traceability on the other side [4]. Being service-oriented, a framework thus allows to (i) use identified security elements for (strategic) decision (acquisition of services in the infrastructure) and/or (ii) to take actions to mitigate threats within the service adoption/development [5];
- **Support for Business IT Alignment (BITA)**. BITA refers to the application of IT in an appropriate and timely manner and in harmony with business needs, goals, and strategies [6]. According to Mayer et al. [7], RM methods have the main objective of guaranteeing "*some specific form of business/IT alignment, accrediting that the right level of security solution is put in place, with respect to the value of the assets of the organization to be protected*". This is especially important here because we are interested

in seeing how the management level elements impact the realization of the business and IT strategies [8]. This allows us to trace security from the management level to the governance level and vice versa;

- **Goal-oriented.** Goals play a key role for domain understanding and stakeholders' intention elicitation [9]. Goal-orientation refers to the focus on the strategies pursued by individual actors or an entire organization. Goal-oriented methods allow making interrogative questions, analysing consequences of decisions, and explore solution spaces [9]. They allow to model strategic goals desired by some stakeholders and aimed to lead the organization to an enhanced competitive position.

Security is about balancing the trade-offs between the competing goals of multiple actors [10]. Being goal-oriented is crucial for a security aware framework as it allows to capture the impact of security concepts on strategic goals and rely on them to make decisions on the adoption of assets;

- **Socially-oriented modeling concepts.** In a social environment, the focus is on *intentionality*, which emanates from actors such as human beings and refers to the fact that there are intents, motivations and reasons behind behaviour of these actors [11, 12]. Moreover, actors do not exist in isolation and can be said to be semi-autonomous. This is because their actions take into consideration their relationships with each other. More precisely, they depend on each other to attain a predefined purpose, which goes beyond individual goals [11, 12]. We believe that taking into account the relation between the parties that are impacted by the future success or failure of an organization is important as it helps us identify people asset or, more precisely, the stakeholders who are contributing to the achievement of strategic objectives and thus, need to be protected. Moreover, according to Yu et al. [12], security and privacy is “*an area in which social modeling is considered to have particular potential*”;
- **Focus on IT development and deployment issues** refers to the fact that rather than addressing problems at the enterprise architecture level,

as mentioned earlier, we are focusing on services and functions with respect to the defined strategies and security criteria;

- **Support for security concerns** to address security requirements, it is important to identify security concepts such as *threats, who threatens, what the threat is directed at* (i.e. asset), etc. As emphasized by the first RO, one of the main objectives of this paper is to identify these security concerns.

Table 1 provides a comparative analysis of the methods/frameworks found through the literature review. Based on the analysis of the available documentation followed by an in-depth discussion among authors to find a consensus on each criteria, the support and the lack of support of each of the methods/frameworks for the listed criteria is indicated by “+” and “-” signs respectively in this table. Based on this table, none of the frameworks supports all six aforementioned criteria, which we consider necessary for embracing security aspects. After analysis we conclude that MoDrIGo best fits our purpose because it outperforms other frameworks by supporting all criteria except *support for security concerns*.

MoDrIGo uses conceptual modeling to support the IT governance process especially for business and IT alignment evaluation when adopting IT services. Within the framework, we have a governance representation and a management representation. While the former allows a graphical representation of the impact of the IT service adoption on the business and IT strategies, the latter allows to identify the elements deployed through the service that impact the strategic objectives.

The MoDrIGo framework allows to “*represent the strategy in terms of business IT objectives and evaluate the impact of business IT services in terms of BITA*” when taking governance-level adoption or development decisions. Using MoDrIGo helps build a custom description of the organization and its strategy [3].

Table 1: A comparative analysis of MoDrIGo and other competing methods

Model or Framework	Criteria						
	Service-driven	Support for BITA		Goal-oriented	Socially-oriented modelling concepts	Support for security concerns	Focus of IT development and deployment issues
		Governance support	Management support				
MoDrIGo [3]	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
ArchiMate [18]	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
Secure Tropos [13]	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
SoSSec [15]	+	-	-	+	-	+	+

All that said, in this study, we choose the MoDrIGo framework as a basis and extend it with security concepts.

2. Running Example: Cyber-Security in Healthcare

Today, we are living in an era where cyber-attacks, rather than a risk or possibility, are an inevitability [16]. Businesses are significantly in the need for constant IT support and organizations must adapt to it. This makes organizations more and more vulnerable to the cyber-attacks [17]. Cyber-security has now become a strategic business priority that CEOs cannot afford to ignore [16]. The damage resulting from a data breach goes far beyond organization data being stolen, the cost of regulatory fines imposed by authorities or, a cleanup [16]. Hidden costs of such loss of commercially sensitive data that is useful to the competitors (e.g. losing the ingredients to Coca Cola) or reputational damage to the brand, can impact the ability of a business to differentiate and as a result its competitiveness in the market. Such costs are difficult to quantify and mostly open-ended [16].

Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM), as part of the telemedicine service, is one of the recent development of healthcare in technology and services and has many advantages in today’s rapid aging population with increasing health complication. Among the advantages, we can refer to reducing the necessary budget for healthcare as well as to provide more convenience for patients while using the hospital information system (HIS) [18, 19]. RPM allows patients to continue their normal daily activities at home while being monitored with the

Figure 1: General overview of the remote patient monitoring system [20]

use of sensor technologies and modern communication. The following figure shows the general model of RPM [20].

Despite the tremendous advantages offered by telemedicine and the RPM service, in many countries, doctors and medical associations refuse to adopt this service between doctors and patients because of vulnerability of personal data, risk of medical malpractice, capital costs for IT systems, and problem with standardisation [18, 21, 22]. To illustrate the threats and vulnerabilities within the healthcare industry, we consider an evolution of the Saint-Romain¹ hospital previously used within the context of the validation of [8]. Let's now consider that, due to the Covid pandemic, the governance board has decided to adopt an RPM service. Being able to identify security threats in such a delicate environment and control them will indeed bring value to Saint-Romain. As such, the more educated the hospital executives and boards become about the involved critical assets and their vulnerabilities, the more effectively they can

¹Wautelet [8] related Saint-Romain as a case study, for confidentiality reasons the real name of the institution was changed. We consider here an evolution of this case but it is here a fictive example for illustrative purpose and thus not a case study.

handle any existing and future threats.

For Saint-Romain, asset identification is the first step in the security requirement elicitation procedure. It refers to the process of determining what information, process, property and people are critical to the mission of the hospital. For example, information assets include HIS, people assets include patients, doctors and nurses along with other persons such as support personnel and visitors and finally business and IT service asset which includes RPM. Regarding the property assets, they consist of both tangible and intangible assets. The former being usually simple to identify - i.e. budget - while the latter, such as hospital's reputation and patient trust, are rather difficult to identify and assign a value.

However, not all assets are critical for Saint-Romain. Critical assets are those assets necessary for Saint-Romain to fulfill its goal of providing healthcare, for without them, processes and functions will fail and lead to the failure of the hospital's mission. In the case of RPM, the authentication information and patient's health records are two of the examples of the most security critical assets. Moreover, the process of communicating patient info with the expert doctor from the remote healthcare device is another security critical asset as in case of being compromised, patient's life will be in danger.

The illustrative example described is used into the next section to illustrate SecureMoDrIGo's constituting concepts.

3. Integrating the SecureMoDrIGo in the IT Governance Process

According to *ISO/IEC 38500* and *Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies (Cobit)* version 5 [23], governance principles and processes can be structured around 3 main stages, i.e. *Evaluate*, *Direct*, and *Monitor*. Figure 2 depicts the three stages of governance principles and processes with respect to our model-driven perspective. In what follows we will show how SecureMoDrIGo applies within these three stages.

Figure 2: Governance Process [3]

3.0.1. Evaluate

According to ISO/IEC 38500, the *Evaluate* stage is referred to as the stage to *evaluate the current and future use of IT* [24]. SecureMoDrIGo allows to, conjunctly with the overall business objectives, represent the security ones of an organization. Moreover the functional aspects of a business IT service can be studied through *i** models enriched with security aspects. By rolling-up the tactical view, the C-suite can study the alignment of the business IT service under consideration for adoption with all of these business objectives. In the evaluate stage, the security issues and the identified threats can be used as factors to mitigate IT services adoption decision.

The instantiation of SecureMoDrIGo’s metamodel onto the case of the hospital depicted from section 4 to 4.2 are typically part of the documentation produced in the Evaluate stage for the C-suite to understand the alignment of the business (and risk strategy) to the IT risks driven by IT service adoption. This documentations (especially the rolled-up impact) is aimed to support them in the decision process.

3.0.2. Direct

Based on the definition of ISO/IEC 38500, the *Direct* stage is meant to *direct the preparation and implementation of the plans and policies to ensure that the use of the software meets the business objectives* [24]. Cybersecurity or IT related security has previously been considered as a technical concept depending exclusively on the management level so of the responsibility of the IT department. Organizations often have budget dedicated to security but they lack knowledge regarding how to best spend this budget. SecureMoDrIGo gives a clear way on how security budgets can be spent within organizations.

Once a positive adoption decision on a business IT service using the SecureMoDrIGo framework has been made, one can use the produced documentation by the framework to direct the devotion of the security effort through implementation/deployment process. The documentation given by the framework does not impose how this should be done but what should at least be tackled. It is like a contract cascaded by the governance level to management one on what needs to be covered security-wise in the way chosen by the latter. Here, the importance of framework's traceability between the governance and the management levels is explicitly shown. So even if the security aspects modeled in SecureMoDrIGo do not change the adoption decision taken by the top-level executives, it might guide the financial flows that are related to IT security support.

Within the case example the managerial-level diagrams (the SRD completed with the vulnerability diagrams) are cascaded to the management level as a contract validated by the governance level that needs to be implemented. The choice of the implementation/deployment approach, technologies and methods remains the choice/responsibility of the management level.

3.0.3. Monitor

Based on the definition of ISO/IEC 38500 the monitor stage is devoted to *monitor the conformance to policies and performance against the plans*.

Monitoring is a stage made after the actual implementation/deployment of the business IT service. The SecureMoDrIGo framework gives a very clear way of pointing out what to focus on security-wise at management level. This gives concrete points to be monitored and reported onto the governance-level. This way, the C-level executives can monitor the measured impact of the security policies that went along the business IT services adoption decisions.

The security logs related to the vulnerabilities identified in the vulnerability diagrams are, after implementation/deployment, reported to the governance level to study the alignment with the set-up decision and analyse possible deviations.

4. SecureMoDrIGo: Model-based Representation of the Business Strategy

Taking into account the example of RPM explained in Section 2 Fig. 3 shows the illustrative governance-level representation of secureMoDrIGo. Through this representation, it is possible to represent the security element, represented by a cloud annotated letter “S” positioned at its center, that plays an important role at the strategic level of an organization (here the Saint-Romain healthcare institution).

The new (security) element added to the strategic representation is *security goal* which refers to the high level security goals of Saint-Romain. As shown in the diagram, security objectives are refinements of strategic objectives meaning that they need to be fulfilled so that their parent strategic objectives can be achieved.

As it is depicted in Fig. 3 to securely achieve the strategic objective “*Expand the use of technology to deliver service to patients in hospitals as well as in remote locations*”, Saint-Romain should first fulfill the security objective *Deliver service through safe and secure platform*. In other words, while Saint-Romain aims to expand the use of technology, it should not ignore the importance of protecting the life of its patients and their data and sensitive information.

Figure 3: SecureMoDrIGo's strategic-level representation

4.1. The RPM Service: Linking Management Level Elements with Strategic Objectives

Defining the concept of *security goal* at the strategic level is important as it allows organizations to trace high-level security aspects that are part of each strategic goal.

Furthermore, it allows to take (strategic) decisions aligned with the identified security policy. This section is devoted to the study of the management level elements that will impact the realization of the strategic objectives. For that, we depict the RPM business-IT service. In our specific context, it also allows to study the alignment between the strategic objectives and the management level elements including security. To avoid the scalability issues, we focus on a small part of the RPM service and its security related aspects as an illustrative example. Moreover, we break down the management-level representation diagram into different diagrams: the main Strategic Rational diagram (see Fig. 5), where we see the details of the implementation of the RPM service, and the vulnerability diagrams (see Fig. 6 and Fig. 7) where the security related elements are presented. The three diagrams together illustrate the management-level

representation of the RPM service enhanced by relevant security elements.

Figure 4: Legend - elements used within the management-level representation

Fig. 4 depicts the elements used within the three diagrams. As it is shown, the enhanced management level also includes the security elements which are annotated with letter “S” (positioned at their center), except for the vulnerability element. These elements include: *threat* (represented with a pentagon), *vulnerability* (represented with a lock), *incident* (represented with an explosion element), *security control* (represented with a hexagon), *security control objective* (represented by an oval), and finally the *exploit* and the *enables* links. In Figure 5, vulnerabilities are represented by a *lock*. These vulnerabilities are further represented in vulnerability diagrams presented in Figure 6 and 7². The former provides an example of the login credentials resource and the latter an example of the Remote Healthcare Device actor. The two examples are further explained hereafter:

- *Example 1. Vulnerability associated to a resource.* In order to enter the RPM system, the physician should provide its login credentials. Providing a weak password is a vulnerability that can lead to security threats and

²Note that, there can be many possible vulnerabilities in this diagram but for the sake of scalability, we give an example of only two

Figure 5: Strategic Rationale Diagram Representing SecureMoDrIGo’s management-level representation for the RPM Service Adoption

incidents. As it is shown in Fig. 6 when the physician provides a weak password (vulnerability), phishing (threat) can happen, which then leads to health protected data being accessed (incident). In order to avoid such security threat and incident, the healthcare should put in place multi-layer login protocol (security control). The latter will also help maintain the security requirement of login credentials (strong password), and helps Saint-Romain achieve its security objective *deliver health services through safe and secure platform*.

- *Example 2. Vulnerability associated to an actor.*

The remote healthcare device has different vulnerabilities, among them, *lack of proper documentation of the security posture of the device*. Once the latter is exploited, the attacker can take over the device (threat) which then leads to the generation of false alarm (incident). Using firewalls and virtual private networks will avoid such threat and incident. Furthermore, it will help maintaining the availability of the device (security requirement) and achieving the security objective of the healthcare which is delivering

Figure 6: Vulnerability Diagram for the *login_credentials* Resource

health service through safe and secure platform.

Following the management-level representation, it is possible to see the traceability between the strategic and management levels. Together, such security alignment between the strategic and the management level will mitigate similar future threats and incidents. Furthermore, modeling the associated security requirements for each strategic goal helps the governance board with informed decision making by considering the threats that each strategic goal reflects at the management level, which answers our main RQ.

4.2. Rolling-up the Impact of Business IT Services on the Business and Security Strategies

The impact of management level elements on the business and strategy was explicitly highlighted in the previous section. This section depicts how the individual impacts (positive and negative) are aggregated on the highest level. Figure 8 depicts the impact of RPM service adoption at the management level representation (see figures 5, 6, and 7) onto the business and security strategies. This allows the governance level managers to see how the acquisition of new IT services influences the strategic objectives and more precisely the security objectives of the organization and helps them decide on the adoption of such

Figure 7: Vulnerability Diagram for the *Remote Healthcare Device Actor*

service.

The new construct added to the strategic representation is *Business-IT service* and is represented by a cloud outlined with a dashed line, which in the case of Saint-Romain represents the RPM service.

5. Distinction/Comparison between the SecureMoDrIGO framework VS the security frameworks used by the Telecom company

This section provides a distinctive/comparative analysis between the SecureMoDrIGO framework, and the security frameworks used by the Telecom company. This analysis is done to (1) identify and propose potential improvements that can be applied to the SecureMoDrIGO framework and (2) evaluate the thoroughness of the SecureMoDrIGO framework compared to other security frameworks.

The Telecom company currently uses security control frameworks such as NIST & CIS20. The Telecom company is currently striving to adopt the STRIDE model and has been using some Deloitte proprietary Capability Maturity frameworks.

For this research study, both the NIST and CIS20 frameworks will be com-

Figure 8: Strategic-level representation enhanced with security

pared against the SecureMoDrIGo framework. Although, both frameworks are mainly tailored to security risk mitigation and management it can be interesting to investigate if they are aspects of these frameworks that can be integrated into SecureMoDrIGo.

NIST Framework VS The SecureMoDrIGo framework

NIST is the National Institute of Standards and Technology at the U.S. Department of Commerce. The NIST Cybersecurity Framework aids businesses of all sizes in understanding, managing, and decreasing cybersecurity risk, as well as safeguarding their networks and data. The framework provides a summary of best practices for businesses to use when deciding where to concentrate their efforts and resources for cybersecurity protection³. The framework contains

³see here: <https://www.ftc.gov/business-guidance/small-businesses/cybersecurity/nist-framework>

industry standards, recommendations, and best practices to facilitate cross-organizational communication of cybersecurity activities and mission objectives at all levels, from executive to high-level implementation and operations⁴. The framework also serves as a top-level security management tool that aids in determining the organization's overall cybersecurity risk⁵.

The framework also provides the organization with consistent language, clarity, and simplicity on extremely complicated matters. The framework helps communicate risks in a way that everyone understands, from the server room to the boardroom⁶. The five core functions of the NIST framework are based on the five stages of risk management. The core functions of the cybersecurity framework include Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover. The **identify stage** consists of identifying what processes and assets need protection. After identifying which assets and processes need protection, the **protect stage** consists of implementing appropriate safeguards to ensure protection of the enterprise's assets. Once the relevant safeguards are in place, the appropriate mechanisms are put in place to detect the occurrence of cybersecurity issues in the detect stage. In the **respond stage**, techniques are developed to contain the impact of cybersecurity events. Finally, the **recover stage** is the last phase in which the necessary procedures are put in place to restore capabilities and services that have been harmed by cybersecurity events⁷.

The NIST framework primarily focuses on risk management and assessment whilst the SecureMoDrIGo framework does not provide any risk assessment or risk management functions. The SecureMoDrIGo framework provides a multiple-level security overview and serves as a decision-making tool for organizations regarding asset adoption. Specifically, the framework allows managers and executives to make decisions on the adoption of new IT services. The SecureMoDrIGo focuses on 3 main core functions: **Evaluate**, **Direct**, and

⁴see here: <https://www.cybersaint.io/blog/nist-cybersecurity-framework-core-explained>

⁵see here: <https://www.balbix.com/insights/nist-cybersecurity-framework/>

⁶see here: <https://www.nist.gov/video/cybersecurity-framework-0>

⁷see here: <https://www.balbix.com/insights/nist-cybersecurity-framework/>

Monitor. In the **Evaluate** stage, the current and future use of IT is evaluated. SecureMoDrIGo allows for traceability between the management and governance levels. By rolling up to the governance level, C-level executives can study the alignment between the business IT service (the service that is being considered for adoption) and the business objectives of the service. The potential security concerns and threats identified within the vulnerability diagrams can be used as factors when considering which security controls to implement. In the **Direct** stage, the preparation and the implementation of plans and policies are directed to ensure that the use of the software meets the business objective (ensuring BITA). The produced documentation provided by the framework directs the devotion of the security effort through the implementation/deployment process (focuses on how the security efforts should be tackled). In the **Monitor** stage, the conformance to policies is monitored. The framework makes evident what to focus on security-wise at management level. All identified security-wise management aspects need to be monitored and reported to the governance level. The five core functions of the NIST framework are Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover as listed and explained in the previous paragraph.

A common similarity between both frameworks is that they provide a guide as to how physical, financial resources should be distributed security-wise. The NIST framework offers a summary of best practices that companies can utilize to determine where to focus their security efforts. The SecureMoDrIGo framework provides a clear understanding on how security budgets can be spent within organizations.

CIS20 framework VS The SecureMoDrIGo framework

The Center for Internet Security (CIS) Top 20 Critical Security Controls (CSC) is a prioritized set of best practices created to stop the most pervasive and dangerous threats of today⁸. The CIS 20 Security controls help to mitigate risks by having a solid security foundation on which to build industry or business

⁸see here: <https://foresite.com/blog/introduction-to-the-cis-20-controls/>

specific security protocols⁹. The CIS Critical Security Controls are actionable measures that are designed to create higher overall cybersecurity defense and assist organizations in better defending against common cyber-attacks¹⁰. To counter the most common types of cyber-attacks and safeguard digital assets, knowledge is gathered from a wide range of security specialists, distilled, and explained by industry experts, and presented in a manner that can easily be customized by any business. These 20 critical security controls enable IT workers to respond quickly and successfully to escalating security concerns, enabling organizations to mitigate cybersecurity risks. The effects of implementing the CSC are astounding; studies have shown that even just the most basic use of the CSC may prevent 85% of cyberattacks¹¹. The CIS benchmarks take into account the fact that most businesses must select priorities because resources are frequently constrained. Therefore, regardless of the industry type, CIS divides the controls into three categories: fundamental, organizational, and basic. The CIS CSC recommendations differ from other security controls and lists due to this standardization¹².

The CIS20 framework differs from the SecureMoDrIGo framework immensely. The number one differentiating factor being that SecureMoDrIGo is focused on depicting how security elements influence the security objectives at management level. When drilling up to the governance level, it is observable how the business IT service influences the construction of strategic objectives, and more specifically security objectives. The CIS20 framework focuses on risk mitigation and explains how the 20 critical security controls can prevent prevalent cyber-attacks from occurring¹³. Even though these two frameworks are very different, the CIS20 provides a set of security controls that can be used when creating the CASE tool for SecureMoDrIGo. “Having an extensive list of security controls

⁹see here: <https://ordr.net/article/complete-guide-to-cis-critical-security-controls/>

¹⁰see here: <https://www.rapid7.com/fundamentals/cis-critical-security-controls/>

¹¹see here: <https://ordr.net/article/complete-guide-to-cis-critical-security-controls/>

¹²see here: <https://www.rapid7.com/fundamentals/cis-critical-security-controls/>

¹³see here: <https://ordr.net/article/complete-guide-to-cis-critical-security-controls/>

that modelers can choose from, makes it easier to construct the vulnerability diagrams”- Team member from the Telecom company.

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Chapter 4

Supporting Digital Transformation Strategy Formulation through a Customizable Set of Generic Objectives: Conceptual Model and Expert Opinions

Appendix A The DT Objectives and The Associated Sources

The following table lists the DT objectives and the related sources from which these DT objectives were identified.

Table A1: Key DT objectives and the respective sources

Key Digital Transformation Objectives		Number of Related Articles
	Digital Roadmap	Gimpel et al. (2018), Chantias et al. (2019), Sia et al. (2016), Zaoui & Souissi (2021), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hess et al. (2016), Holgeid et al. (2018), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Loonam et al. (2018), Parviainen et al. (2017), Brown & Brown (2019), Vey et al. (2017), Zaoui et al. (2020), Gobble (2018)
	Risk-taking, risk and Technology Appetite	Sia et al. (2016), Hirt & Willmott (2014), Chantias & Hess (2016), Matt et al. (2015), Vial (2019), Kane et al. (2015), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Porter & Heppelmann (2014), Yoo et al. (2012), Hess et al. (2016), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Andriole (2017), Kane et al. (2016), Trenkle (2019), Holgeid et al. (2018), Main et al. (2018), Parviainen et al. (2017), El Sawy et al (2016), Fitzgerald et al. (2013), Duerr et al. (2018), Yucel (2018), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Haffke et al. (2016), Haffke et al. (2017), Hartl & Hess (2017), Dixon et al. (2017), Brown & Brown (2019), Wiesbock & Hess (2019), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Vogelsang et al. (2019), Catlin et al. (2015), Leonhardt et al. (2017), Habtay & Holmen (2014), Vey et al. (2017), Correani et al. (2020), Gobble (2018)

	<p>Agile Mindset, Organizational agility, Agile IT</p>	<p>Sia et al. (2016), Warner & Wager (2019), Dang & Vartiainen (2019), Gimpel et al. (2018), Ranjan & Mishra (2019), Matt et al. (2015), Chanias et al. (2019), Yeow et al. (2018), Vial (2019), Kane et al. (2015), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Heavin & Power (2018), Ismail et al. (2017), Bharadwaj et al. (2013), Hess et al. (2016), Kane et al. (2016), Correani et al. (2020), Sebastian et al. (2017), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Karimi & Walter (2015), Legner et al. (2017), Loonam et al. (2018), Chan et al. (2018), Heavin et al. (2018), Dremel et al. (2017), Weill & Woerner (2017), Maine et al. (2018), El Sawy et al (2016), Duerr et al. (2018), Yucel (2018), Nadeem et al. (2018), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Berghaus & Back (2017), Haffke et al. (2016), Haffke et al. (2017), Hartl & Hess (2017), Piccinini et al. (2015), Dixon et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2011), Brown & Brown (2019), Gobble (2018), Wiesbock & Hess (2019), Muehlburger et al. (2019), Zaoui et al. (2020), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Catlin et al. (2015), Leonhardt et al. (2017), Tumbas et al. (2017), Vey et al. (2017), Zaoui & Souissi (2021)</p>
<p>Strategic Changes and Digital Maturity</p>	<p>Dynamic/digital Capabilities</p>	<p>Sia et al. (2016), Warner & Wager (2019), Dang & Vartiainen (2019), Chanias et al. (2019), Yeow et al. (2018), North et al. (2019), Chanias & Hess (2016), Kane et al. (2016), Vial (2019), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hess et al. (2016), Karimi & Walter (2015), Yoo et al. (2012), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Loonam et al. (2018), Svahn et al. (2017), Legner et al. (2017), Dremel et al. (2017), Nylen & Holmstrom (2015), Parviainen et al. (2017), El Sawy et al (2016), Duerr et al. (2018), Nadeem et al. (2018), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Dixon et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2011), Setia et al. (2013), Wiesbock & Hess (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Ferreira et al. (2020), Catlin et al. (2015), Tumbas et al. (2017)</p>

	Operational Efficiency	<p>Dang & Vartiainen (2019), Warner & Wager (2019), Chanias et al. (2019), Chanias & Hess (2016), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hess et al. (2016), Sia et al. (2016), Kohli & Johnson (2011), Loonam et al. (2018), Porter & Heppelmann (2014), Westerman et al. (2011), Peter et al. (2019), Bughin & Van Zeebroeck (2017), Gimpel et al. (2018), Ismail et al. (2017), Ross et al. (2016), Singh & Hess (2017), Vial (2019), Sebastian et al. (2017), Trenkle (2019), Holgeid et al. (2018), Weill & Woerner (2017), Zaoui et al. (2020), El Sawy et al (2016), Fitzgerald et al. (2013), Westerman et al. (2014), Nadeem et al. (2018), Westerman et al. (2011), Westerman & Bonnet (2015), Bharadwaj et al. (2013a), Piccinini et al. (2015), Brown & Brown (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Ferreira et al. (2020), Ghosh et al. (2018), Roecker et al. (2017), Correani et al. (2020), Heavin et al. (2018)</p>
	Customer Behaviour Analysis	<p>Hirt & Willmott (2014), Warner & Wager (2019), Chanias et al. (2019), Chanias & Hess (2016), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hess et al. (2016), Sia et al. (2016), Westerman et al. (2011), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Yeow et al. (2018), Hansen & Sia (2015), Peter et al. (2019), Gobble (2018), Loonam et al. (2018), Porter & Heppelmann (2014), Correani et al. (2020), Bughin & Van Zeebroeck (2017), Gimpel et al. (2018), Heavin & Power (2018), Ismail et al. (2017), Ross et al. (2016), Singh & Hess (2017), Heavin et al. (2018), Sebastian et al. (2017), Karimi & Walter (2015), Legner et al. (2017), Trenkle (2019), Holgeid et al. (2018), Durr et al. (2017), Zaoui et al. (2020), Nylen & Holmstrom (2015), Weill & Woerner (2017), Main et al. (2018), Oestreicher-Singer & Zalmanson (2013), Parviainen et al. (2017), El Sawy et al (2016), Fitzgerald et al. (2013), Westerman et al. (2014), Duerr et al. (2018), Yucel (2018), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Zaoui & Souissi (2021), Berghaus & Back (2017), Haffke et al. (2016), Hartl & Hess (2017), Piccinini et al. (2015), Setia et al. (2013), Wiesbock & Hess (2019), Muehlburger et al. (2019), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Ferreira et al. (2020), Ghosh et al. (2018), Catlin et al. (2015), Liere-Netheler et al. (2018), Leonhardt et al. (2017), Tumbas et al. (2017), Habtay & Holmen (2014), Vey et al. (2017), Roecker et al. (2017)</p>
Changes in Value Creation	Digital and Traditional Offerings Alignment	<p>Hirt & Willmott (2014), Hess et al. (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hansen & Sia (2015), Westerman et al. (2014), Loonam et al. (2018), Duerr et al. (2018), Zaoui et al. (2020), Correani et al. (2020)</p>

	Transformational Leadership	Warner & Wager (2019), Chantias et al. (2019), Chantias & Hess (2016), Spitzer et al. (2013), Matt et al. (2015), Sia et al. (2016), Kohli & Johnson (2011), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Hess et al. (2016), Peter et al. (2019), Gimpel et al. (2018), Bankewitz et al. (2016), Loonam et al. (2018), Andriole (2017), Heavin & Power (2018), Ismail et al. (2017), Vial (2019), Legner et al. (2017), Hansen et al. (2011), Trenkle (2019), Holgeid et al. (2018), Dremel et al. (2017), Weill & Woerner (2017), Oestreicher-Singer & Zalmanson (2013), Parviainen et al. (2017), El Sawy et al (2016), Fitzgerald et al. (2013), Westerman et al. (2014), Nadeem et al. (2018), Westerman et al. (2011), Westerman & Bonnet (2015), Berghaus & Back (2017), Bharadwaj et al. (2013a), Haffke et al. (2016), Haffke et al. (2017), Dixon et al. (2017), Brown & Brown (2019), Wiesbock & Hess (2019), Heavin et al. (2018), Muehlburger et al. (2019), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Ghosh et al. (2018), Catlin et al. (2015)
	Digital Skill set and Mindset	Spitzer et al. (2013), Dang & Vartiainen (2019), Chantias et al. (2019), Chantias & Hess (2016), Vial (2019), Matt et al. (2015), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Peter et al. (2019), Gimpel et al. (2018), Hess et al. (2016), Ismail et al. (2017), Kane et al. (2016), Svahn et al. (2017), Dremel et al. (2017), Nylen & Holmstrom (2015), Main et al. (2018), El Sawy et al (2016), Duerr et al. (2018), Yucel (2018), Nadeem et al. (2018), Westerman et al. (2014), Westerman et al. (2011), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Bharadwaj et al. (2013a), Hartl & Hess (2017), Brown & Brown (2019), Muehlburger et al. (2019), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Vogelsang et al. (2019), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Ferreira et al. (2020), Ghosh et al. (2018), Liere-Netheler et al. (2018), Habtay & Holmen (2014), Vey et al. (2017), Roecker et al. (2017), Heavin et al. (2018), Gobble (2018), Zaoui & Souissi (2021)
Changes in Organizational Structure	A Separate Digital Unit	Warner & Wager (2019), Chantias et al. (2019), Chantias & Hess (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Hess et al. (2016), Hansen & Sia (2015), Ismail et al. (2017), Yeow et al. (2018), Holotiuk & Beimborn (2017), Singh & Hess (2017), Vial (2019), Matt et al. (2015), Karimi & Walter (2015), Fitzgerald et al. (2013), Duerr et al. (2018), Westerman et al. (2014), Bilgeri & Wortmann (2017), Correani et al. (2020)

Financial Constraint	Hess et al. (2016), North et al. (2019), Matt et al. (2015), Ismail et al. (2017), Vial (2019), Parviainen et al. (2017), Chantias & Hess (2016), Karimi & Walter (2015), Trenkle (2019), Duerr et al. (2018), Yucel (2018), Nadeem et al. (2018), Osmundsen et al. (2018), Haffke et al. (2016), Haffke et al. (2017), Nwankpa & Roumani (2016), Piccinini et al. (2015), van Dyk & Van Belle (2019), Vogelsang et al. (2019), Ghosh et al. (2018), Zaoui et al. (2020), Zaoui & Souissi (2021)
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Appendix B Detailed explanation of DT objectives

- Develop a Digital Roadmap

- Develop and Assess Digital Maturity

Digital strategy drives digital maturity [4]. It is not possible to execute a DTS without performing a digital maturity assessment [73]. According to Kane et al. [4], in a digitally mature organization, digital has transformed business models, processes, and talent engagement. According to their research, among organizations who are at the early stages of digital maturity, only 15% have a clear and coherent digital strategy. This is while more than 80% of digitally mature organizations do. On the other hand, assessing digital maturity of the organization helps to check if the formulated strategy requires more elaboration [6]. According to Ranjan and Mishra [73], assessment parameters include leadership, culture, technology, process and ecosystems. For each of these parameters, a variety of attributes are analysed. As an example, leadership is rated based on organization structure, governance, and vision and mission [73].

- * Develop Agile Mindset

Due to the complexity and dynamism of the business and technology environment, organizations may not be capable of fully articulating their DTS upfront [74]. Such environmental dynamism suggests that digital strategy is iterative, emergent, and impacted by evolving organizational capabilities [74]. According to Holotiuk et al. [63], agility is in the DNA of DTS. DTS builds upon organizational agility to allow for rapid adaptation [4]. Likewise, Chantias et al. [6] emphasize the importance of establishing an agile working mode for formulating DTS. According to them, DTS needs to be constantly revised and reworked by incorporating new insights and learning from ongoing implementation efforts. They define five DTS practices, one being “*working business and customer-centric as well as agile and innovation-oriented*”.

On the other hand, since diffusion of digital technologies can alter swiftly, there typically is high uncertainty regarding the underlying assumptions of DT strategies [3]. Therefore, DT strategies need to be subject to continuous reassessment, in which transformational progress as well as the underlying assumptions to date are evaluated. Having clear procedures on the reassessment of DTS is necessary so that organizations can take early actions in case expectations are not met. This concerns the intervals between reassessments, as well as the definition of measures and procedures to assess intermediate progress and threshold on which corrective actions can be taken [3].

Furthermore, organizations should adopt an agile technology development mindset to test new concepts and ideas, be collaborative, and rule out approaches that do not work (i.e. fail fast). This includes an iterative approach to deliver a solution (MVP), continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) and a DevOps model [73]. As an example, instead of digitalizing the entire supply chain, an organization should start with a measurable, modest goal such as implementing a demand predicting solution and integrating it with their ERP [73, 75].

* Assess Risk and Technology Appetite

As already mentioned in Section 2, one of the key dimensions of DTS is the use of technology, which addresses an organization's attitude to wards new technologies, and its ability to exploit these technologies [3]. According to Kane et al. [4], organizations with high digital maturity are more comfortable taking risks than peers with less digital maturity. They argue that in the context of DT, risk-taking is becoming a cultural norm. This is because more digitally advanced organizations seek new levels of competitive advantage.

Likewise, Matt et al. [3] state that an organization can decide whether it desires to become a technological market leader with the ability to create its own technological standards, or whether it sees technologies as means to realize business operations and opts for resorting to already established standards. Despite of the advantages, being a market leader in technology might be more risky. More precisely, although further deviations from the classical core businesses - caused by new digital activities offers more opportunities, they are often accompanied with higher risks that can result from less experience in the new field [3].

* Develop Dynamic Capabilities (DC)

DC refers to "the capacity of an organization to create, extend or modify its resource base" [76]. It helps an organization to be in tune with the dynamic requirements of the digital marketplace [7]. According to Hess et al. [7], the rapid digital scaling ability of

an organization is due to its DC which results from fusing digital infrastructure and business strategy.

The importance of DC in a digital world lies in the fact that it links the strategic choices of an organization with environmental circumstances. Moreover, it addresses how organizations direct their resources and capabilities to gain a sustained competitive advantage in environments that are significantly impacted by new technologies [77]. Bankewitz et al. [77] also emphasize on the importance of DC by stating that within organizations DC are maintained through sensing, seizing, and re-configuring and orchestrating assets (i.e. elements of their business models) accordingly. Likewise, Yeow et al. [74] states that at the broad level, DC entail three capacities: sensing, seizing, and transforming.

- Sense disruptions and changes in the market

In their research, Chantias et al. [6] conduct a case study and analyse the way pre-digital organizations can develop a DTS. They recognize seven main phases that summarize the interplay of context, content and process during DTS formulation and implementation. According to their study, during the first phase, the pre-digital organization checks to see if it is experiencing any pressure for DT. This can be either from its shareholders, customers (i.e. changing customer behaviour) or competitors (i.e. being aware of any technological approaches that can be perceived as a disruptive threat to its core business).

Digital technologies provide “*both game-changing opportunities for - and existential threats to - companies*” [17]. DT can be viewed as an exogenous threat that disrupts the competitive environment [25]. Such digital disruption requires a response from organizations that seek to change their ways of value creation - traditionally used to stay competitive - and is often explained by formulating a proper strategy [25, 78]. Sensing refers to the identification of opportunities before they occur and recognizing competitive threats [77].

- Seize upon trends

To formulate a digital strategy, an organization should be able to seize upon trends and emerging technologies [25]. At the same time, an organization should be aware of the huge risks and opportunities that can be brought on by DT [31]. Seizing is about responding to threats and opportunities (through strategic responses), associated with rapid technological change, that have been sensed [25, 77]. One of the ways to sense and seize new opportunities is to take advantage of the crowd [79]. This is mainly because of the

- great use of social networks and media, and digital devices, which entail increasing online collaboration in the crowd [77].
- **Develop and Reconfigure Business and IT Resources**
 Chaniyas et al. [6] argue that a DTS needs to be aligned with business and IT strategies and does not necessarily replace them. Likewise, Matt et al. [3] argue that same as in previous discussion on business IT alignment [80], it is important to obtain a close fit between DT strategies, IT strategies, and other organizational and functional strategies. Following this, Yeow et al. [74] argue that based on the fact that digital strategy can be seen as a fusion of business and IT strategies, today, rather than focusing to align business and IT strategies, it is more relevant to *align the ongoing IT and business resources with the emerging DTS*. “*The technology should be made to fit with any proposed business model innovation*” [81]. When an organization sense the need to digitalize, it would need to develop and iteratively reconfigure resources, and refine strategy to achieve an alignment between the emerging DTS and the existing organizational resources [82]. In case of misalignment, organizations will fail to respond to internal tensions and changes in the environment [74, 79].
 - **Define Board’s Vision and Strategic Direction**
 Depending on their strategic vision for digital technologies as well as their individual business models, organizations choose a different approach to DT [7]. Digital vision and mission statements are both essential components of an organization’s strategy [73]. To formulate a DTS, the vision of the CEO and its strategic priorities (i.e. creation of new business models, process automation, customer excitement, etc.) should be clear to DTU [6].
 - **Assess Capability and Compatibility of IS**
 DT is driven by the emergence of digital technologies. Therefore, an organization’s attitude towards new technologies [3] as well as its approach to explore and use new digital technologies are part of an essential dimension of DTS, *use of technology* [7]. This implies that organizations should perceive IT as their core competency and not only having IT department that mainly focused on keeping IT operations running. IT department should have the willingness and adequate competencies to attain any form of digital innovation [6]. Managers should evaluate the role of their IT departments as well as assessing how innovative and proactive they are when it comes to DT [7].
 - **Evaluate and Prioritise Digital Ideas**
 According to Bankewitz et al. [77], in order to create value for organizations, boards should get involved in strategic decisions that concern

and impact digital technologies. Subsequently, they can provide significant value by checking that digital technology priorities and investment choices will minimise risks and maximise returns, challenging the main assumptions, and seizing technological opportunities before they materialise.

Not all ideas are practical or an immediate priority [73]. Therefore, different issues ideas should be evaluated and prioritized on the basis of criteria such as “ease of adoption and use”, “strategic fitness”, “help in competitive advantage”, “time taken to realize benefit”, “total cost”, “degree of stakeholder buy in”, “risk mitigation”, “operational effectiveness”, and “financial benefit” [73].

- Identify Structural Changes

- Foster Transformational Leadership

One of the important internal driver of DT is board’s leadership [6]. Digital and business goals should be aligned through leadership alignment and stakeholder buy-in [73]. A visionary leadership is required to see the role of DT in helping to ensure the future viability of an organization [6]. At the same time this leadership should be of cooperative style, meaning that instead of communicating its DT as “getting ahead of the digital tsunami”, top management communicates it as “surfing the digital wave”. This requires all managers to share the same mindset of the board and avoid being reluctant to change [6].

According to Kane et al. [4], “*the digital agenda is led from the top*”. They state that leaders do not need to be technology wizards but they must understand what can be done at the intersection of business and technology (i.e. digital fluency). Moreover, they should be ready to lead the way in conceptualizing how business can be transformed by technology. Moreover, DT strategies affect the entire company, and thus their execution may result in resistance from different organizational areas. To deal with such resistance, it is essential to foster transformation leadership skills ensure that the stakeholders who are affected by the transformation, are actively involved [3].

- Foster Digital Skill Set and Mindset

Digital is not only about technology but integrating technology with a shift in mindset [83]. DT is often accompanied by change in skill sets that are not only required for the transformation itself, but for subsequent regular operations as well [3]. Such digital mindset should be driven from the top, and should be agile [73]. In other words, boards must ensure that their organizations foster a digital mindset while being able to respond to the disruptions associated the emerging usage of digital technologies [7, 77]. Ranjan et al. [73] believe that successful digital organizations start by thinking digital. They instil a culture of challenging any/all processes and practices; establishing such culture - such that it will derive digital - should be an important priority. According to them, a digital mindset

entails four important points: *start by defining what digital means, inculcating the culture that establishes a shift in the mindset, take a holistic view of people, process and technology and in-source critical skills.*

According to Kane et al. [4], digitally maturing organizations build skills to realize the strategy. They add that conceptualizing the impact of digital technologies on business is an important skill that is lacking in many organizations at the early phases of digital maturity [4]. Moreover, in the context of DT, changes to the organizational culture and structure lead employees to take roles that were traditionally outside their function [7]. While current employees may have a less tech-savvy mindset and may require the necessary technological capability (or digital capabilities [60]) to cope with the imminent changes, new focused and highly skilled employees might be difficult to find [3]. As such, Organizations require guidance on the evaluation of existing technological capabilities as well as guidance on designing the training procedures for current and future employees [3].

- Establish a Digital Transformation Unit (DTU)

According to Chanas et al. [6], in order to realize a DTS, it is necessary to have a dedicated DTU that operates autonomously and separately from the IT department. This unit has its own staff - employees mostly delegated from other departments - and DT board directed by Chief Digital Officer (CDO) [3, 7, 25, 63, 74] and acts as an internal service unit as well as a think tank for the organization.

One of the main task of DTU is to formulate DTS [6]. The creation of CDO position indicates the strategic nature of DT [3]. CIO may also manage the transformation, especially if the focus is on business processes. Therefore, for organizations employing both a CDO and a CIO, there should be a concrete alignment between the two [3, 7]. They should actively communicate and closely coordinate their initiatives and strategies [7].

CDO should ensure that digital technologies are leveraged in proper way and are aligned with the organizational objectives [25]. Moreover, he/she should directly align his/her incentives with the processes and targets of the strategy, and should have enough experience in transformational projects [3]. CDO should directly report the digital progress to CEO and proactively interact with him/her [73].

- Identify Possible Changes in Value Creation and Operational Efficiency
Some of the key transformational opportunities [60] that lead to value creation are listed below:

- Identify Processes that can be enhanced by digital technology

The scope of DTS goes beyond the digitization of resources. It involves the use of advanced IT, the transformation of key organizational and structural aspects or value creation aspects including key products and services, which result in adjusted or completely new business models [4]. Taking into account a music industry, the rising demand for internet-based media

leads to the changes of entire business models [7].

Digital technologies can transform organization's business models, operations, products and services, as well as its competitive environment [7, 84–86]. Unlike born-digital organizations such as Amazon, pre-digital organizations often need to change their business model, processes and their entire organization as they adopt digital technologies [20, 63, 87].

In the context of DT, business models and operational processes are known as two of the key transformed areas of initiatives [60]. DT usually leads to altering or redefinition of business models [6]. To mitigate threats or exploit identified opportunities of DT, organizations have to revise their business strategies and decide whether to develop new business models or to adapt to current ones [79]. According to the case study conducted by Chanas et al. [6], although the digitalization project is mainly targeting a specific business model of the organization, it can also trigger a whole chain of additional considerations in the organization.

- Follow, Analyse and Anticipate Consumer Behaviour and Expectations Successful organizations consider customers in their strategy [73]. Today consumers have ubiquitous access to information and their communication capabilities have increased [25]. According to Chanas et al. [6], recognizing the need for DT is an initial phase of formulating DTS. *Changing customer behaviour* is one of the factors that can raise awareness about the possible need for a holistic DT. Hess et al. [7] also emphasises the importance of following customers into the digital world and generating customer experiences. The case study of DBS Bank [88] illustrates the importance of anticipating customer expectation. According to this case study, Asian consumers expect to carry out most of their banking operations through mobile digital banking solutions. Under the pressure created by these expectations, DBS should now offer new services to remain competitive in the environment where banks are put under siege by digital revolution. Therefore, it has become a strategic imperative for organizations to *anticipate* changes in consumer expectations rather than responding to these changes.
- Establish Synergy Between Digital and Traditional Offerings Successful digital organizations actively foster synergy between traditional and digital offerings [7]. According to Holotiuk et al. [63], business models have to blur boundaries between physical stores and online shops in order to *integrate physical and digital worlds*. Ranjan and Mishra [73] emphasize this synergy by taking the Nordstrom case as an example. One of the main innovation of this store has been its seamless UX meaning that the store provides the same feel and look on the cloud (website) as it does in its bricks-and-mortar [73]. Furthermore, new technologies can be used to improve the use of traditional technologies such as CRM or ERP [75].

- Financial Constraints

Appendix C Interview Description

The interviews were conducted individually via online conferencing software such as Skype, Microsoft Teams, or Zoom. The number of interviewees was six. As such, six semi-structured interviews were held during March and April. These semi-structured interviews were drafted, inspired by the Interview Protocol Refinement Framework (IPR) as presented by Castillo-Montoya [67], to ensure the questions asked aligned with the research question and inquiry-based conversations were held.

The interviews ranged in duration from 00:51:40 to 01:29:53, with an average of 01:01:40, excluding the unrecorded parts. Initially, interviewees were looked for in the researcher's network. Furthermore, potential interviewees were looked for via LinkedIn, in which case a contact request was sent, followed up by a personal message if the request were to be accepted. This personal message inquired the potential interviewee of who the researcher was, the purpose of the study, and the study's goals. The personal message with its information allowed the potential interviewees to assess whether they were fit to answer the questions and provide insights. Practical information concerning the interviews was also given here, together with an invitation to participate in the interview. If accepted, a PDF document was sent at least one week beforehand, containing an explanation concerning the model and its objectives as seen in Appendix B: Provided Explanation.

Before the interview, the purpose, goals and duration of the interview were verbally repeated. Confidentiality was also assured here and permission to record was given by the interviewees. The model was shown to the interviewees and they were asked if everything was clear. The interviewees were encouraged to notify the interviewer immediately whenever anything was unclear.

During the interviews, the model was shown through screen sharing, allowing the interviewees to situate the objectives and follow the model clearly. The interviewees were attentively listened to as to understand and comprehend their opinions and perspectives. Prompt questions were asked whenever appropriate. When there was time left after the interview, the interviewees were asked to provide feedback. Due to time constraints, not every question of the protocol was addressed and thus these results were not included in the results. This feedback concerned the quality of the interview and the interviewer. The profile of each interviewee is shown in Table ??.

To describe the relevant information provided by the interviews, we made use of the NVivo software for qualitative coding. The codes used depended on the corresponding question to which the answers were given. Aspects mentioned by interviewees that did not belong to their respective questions were coded thematically as described by Saunders et al. (2019) [89]. To provide this information, it was necessary first to transcribe the interviews. These interviews were transcribed using intelligent verbatim with the essential parts accurately transcribed. This analytical process ensures that the essence of the interviews was captured and consequently ready to be analyzed.

C.1 Interview Results

- *Transforming Digitally*

Before embarking on the model, it is worthwhile questioning the interviewees regarding the concept of DT. What is understood by DT? What are the main drivers of DT? How is the DT process initiated? Is there a generic strategic model in use? How is the DT process followed up? These are the relevant questions addressed in this section. After all, the start-up and follow-up of the DT process among the interviewees can be an essential source of inspiration to take the first steps towards implementing the model.

When interviewees were asked to describe DT, they answered this question along primarily similar lines. The word “*digitalization*” and the words “*digital technology*” were central here. As Interviewee 2 outlined: “*The finality of a digital transformation is that it contributes to the mission and business objectives of a company, which makes certain choices in terms of customer focus, innovation or operational excellence, then looks for to what extent the digital technologies can inspire and enable, as part of the solution, but not as the complete solution*”. According to Interviewee 2, DT is disruptive and refers to the re-creation of the business, partially or wholly. In the eyes of Interviewee 6, DT is the leveraging of digital technologies that create added value for several stakeholders. Interviewee 3 pointed out the flexibility of the concept due to its constant evolution and confirmed that DT depends on the strategic business objectives. Future relevance was indicated by Interviewee 5, who stated that DT is crucial to remain relevant as a company in the future. Interviewee 1 stated that after a DT process, an organization envisions improved operations. As a starting point, the interviewee cited increasing digitalization rates.

- *Main Drivers Digital Transformation*

What drives DT? The interviewees mentioned several drivers. Interviewee 1; Interviewee 4; Interviewee 5 all mentioned striving for relevance now and in the future to remain competitive as a company. Interviewee 4 elaborated on the innovative aspect and the positioning of the company regarding DT, explaining that they practically live from innovation and developing new methodologies or new services around their products. Interviewee 1; Interviewee 3 looked at it from a customer perspective. Interviewee 1 explained that with the changes in consumer expectations, taking a customer perspective can lead to finding faster and more efficient solutions. Interviewee 2 stated the business objectives, mission, and, more importantly, the value created with the finality of the financial bottom-line as the frame of reference within which DT manifests itself.

- *Digital Transformation Approach*

How is DT approached among the interviewees? Two consultants stated that the strategic orientation of the company is critical. Interviewee 1 stated three questions for this purpose: “*What is the company’s strategy? Why do they want to transform digitally? How are we going to translate this into practice?*” Interviewee 2 added to the strategic orientation that a section

regarding the company's analysis of skills and competencies is also needed. The interviewee added that thinking about digital technologies and how these contribute to a "to-be" operating model can draw inspiration from what peer companies in similar industries are undertaking. Further, the interviewee explained that benchmarking against best practices in peer industries helps determine the axes to achieve a breakthrough. From this extensive assessment flows a gap analysis. The interviewee describes the gap as: "*A gap between where we want to go and what we have today*". The gap analysis is then translated into a roadmap strategy: "*The roadmap is a strategic concrete realization plan over the next three to five years in the different domains that were identified in the gap analysis*". Interviewee 6 described two viewpoints: operational efficiency on the one hand and leveraging digital technologies to improve interaction (with students) on the other. This operational efficiency regards streamlining operations, such as administrative tasks. Interviewee 5 described the benchmark with the sector and the value creation for the end customer, to subsequently derive projects from this. The focus here for the interviewee is on getting the basics right in terms of infrastructure. The plan to implement disruptive technologies is a matter for the future. Interviewee 4 highlighted the growth curve of the digital evolution, which has led them to invest heavily in DT. In doing so, they started developing proof of concepts in different functional areas to see: "*What works, what does not work for us, what creates value for our function, what does not create value for our function*". From this, they designed a kind of governance top-layer to see what they could leverage within their three departments: medical devices, pharma and consumer, with today's focus on automation and integration regarding repetitive, non-value-adding tasks within their functions.

- *Strategic Models in Use*

Are there strategic models in use to plan, implement and monitor the DT process? When interviewees offered answers to this question, the answers were diverse. Two consultants said that planning this process is leaning more toward a particular methodology, toward a particular process (Interviewee 1; Interviewee 3). Interviewee 1 explained that, as an out-of-the-box methodology, they use the scan- focus-act principle. In this, a step-by-step plan is created with as building blocks the customer's strategy or strategies, motivation, best practice to achieve it, and how exactly it will be implemented. To this, the interviewee added that the implementation in itself is always different for each customer, custom-made. Interviewee 3 also stated that it was done through a typical methodology with a customer-specific, tailor- made solution. The interviewee further explained that internal capabilities, technologies and financial aspects are considered. The interviewee further stated that a business case is used to assess the financial end and the external is also mapped out. This external part is formulated in terms of expectations in terms of market adoption.

Interviewee 5; Interviewee 6 stated that they do not have a specific model to embark on the DT process. Interviewee 5 indicated a way of approaching a roadmap, with all types of projects to be accomplished. This roadmap consists of two facets: infrastructure on the one hand and software on the other hand. The implementation is done via the Agile method Azure DevOps to steer the projects in the right direction and adjust when necessary. Interviewee 6 explained using an operating model that defines DT and how and where it takes place. The interviewee further stated that the strategy, consisting of various objectives, is reviewed and validated by the steering committee. The digital strategy here is customized and shaped by experience.

Interviewee 2 stated they use two models for DT: to specify the business strategy and to map out the to-be operating model. In terms of business strategy, they use the value strategy model of Treacy and Wiersema (1993) [90]. This model indicates whether a company must be either innovative, operationally excellent or customer-oriented, and must decide in this respect to continue to operate sustainably. In this manner, the strategic positioning of the company is determined. The second model is used to map out the to-be operating model, taking a holistic approach. The concept they use for this is the Business Process Re-engineering (BPR) model of Hammer and Champy (1993) [91]. This de facto requires a holistic approach, and for this purpose, the interviewee gave some aspects to consider: *“On the one hand, you have to start looking at the processes, activities that you are going to organize. You also have to look at the organization, the competencies that are on board, you have to look at the governance that you set up to test the process, you have to look at the internal culture that has to be aligned with the way you want to manage your processes and the organization. Finally, you need IT (...) for the processes to make you customer-centric or operational excellent”*. He continued his explanation and stated that *“This [concept is used] to structure the organizational model, how you are going to structure yourself as a company on five different axes: Processes, Organization, Governance, Culture and IT”*. Interviewee 2 concluded here that it implies a 360 degrees analysis: not just the digital technology part, as this would not be sustainable competitive.

- *Tracking Digital Transformation Progress*

Are there any particular tools, programs or frameworks in use to monitor the DT process? The answers to this were again diverse. Interviewee 1 stated before proceeding practically to start from a proposal slide. It contains the answers to questions like: *“What do we want to do, why do we want to do this, what do we want to implement?”* The proposal slide is a sort of bottom-line. The monitoring is done by several applications of Microsoft Office, like, for example, Microsoft Planner. For complex projects or Agile projects, they use a specific functionality of JIRA based on Kanban principles. Also, the interviewee mentioned that colleagues run complete digitalization projects

from Miro. Here the interviewee made an analogy to the generic representation: *“It looks somewhat like the model you are showing now, only you can zoom in per branch or cloud again and you can specify even more details. What you often get then is that it actually creates a kind of project structure with the different domains, different topics”*. The interviewee concluded that seldom the same practices are used in terms of using tools and the like. Interviewee 3 stands by this. The interviewee stated that they do not have an official tool in use and that it is a client-specific undertaking, but the business case is consistently used.

Interviewee 6 explained that there is no formal framework in place. However, they do use a dashboard, where various KPI's are reviewed annually. The interviewee further explained that this takes an intuitive approach and is not based on a strict or standard methodology. Interviewee 5 explained that they use Azure DevOps on the software side, including all the user stories. On the support side, they use Freshdesk, a ticketing system. On the infrastructure side, they use Microsoft Planner. To monitor the progress of DT, they hold regular brainstorming moments with the other board members. Further, the interviewee stated to keep DT *“warm”* and maintain the scope of DT.

Interviewee 4 seized on a governance structure for this, in which everything is brought together: *“In the governance structure, we are also going to prioritize more effectively according to: what makes the most sense here? What is our first and second focus? We need to do that prioritization more based on business value, which will then trigger certain aspects of the transformation process”*. Furthermore, the interviewee pointed to a second part, which is also part of the governance structure: the people part. The people part mainly involves change management. The interviewee added that this is the current focus and that it is a huge part. Some questions to be answered: *“What are the roles of the future? How do those roles differ from the roles that staff performs today? Where are those differences situated? How are we going to bridge these differences? Are we going to re-educate our people?”* Through the governance model, they seek to align several functions *“to achieve cross-functional alignment”*. Also, the interviewee stated that they also look externally, taking inspiration from peers and collaborating with consulting firms. The interviewee also confirmed the company's success in digital evolution and backed this up with a top 5 position in Gartner reviews: *“[Gartner] is a neutral entity that assesses different companies on how digital they are evolving”*. The interviewee added that support from high management is present and that they acknowledge the need to transform digitally. Interviewee 4 reiterated the use of the to-be operating model and summarized this process in four steps: *“First, an assessment of the current operation on those different axes, then we work out the to-be situation, and from the gap analysis between the current and future operating model, we are going to formulate a strategy (...) and then from there, we work out a roadmap or timeline”*.

- *The Generic Reference Conceptual Model for DTS*

The focus of the model validation is to find out the strengths, weaknesses and shortcomings of the DTS generic representation. To this end, interviewees were asked whether they thought the strategic objective in question was important and how they had arrived at their opinion. The interviews treated every objective present in the model. If an interviewee disagreed with an objective, he was asked how he arrived at his opinion. If an interviewee saw relevant changes to a particular objective, he was asked to state those. After dealing with each objective, interviewees were asked if the model was complete or not, in which case specific or more general shortcomings were suggested.

The strategic objectives were addressed based on the structure of the model. From left to right, top to bottom and following the analogy of the numeration as represented in Figure 3. This section is divided into six parts; one part for each branch of the model, one part for the general issues and one part for the model as a reference.

- *Branch One*

- *Develop a Digital Roadmap*

When the interviewees were questioned whether developing a digital roadmap is important, the answers were affirmative. Interviewee 3; Interviewee 6 confirmed the importance by stating that the digital roadmap helps structure projects. Interviewee 5 added that the digital roadmap is the foundation. Interviewee 2 confirmed by stating that “80% of companies all agree that developing a digital roadmap is absolutely necessary, as a substantial part of the business plan”. However, the interviewees consistently gave the digital roadmap different meanings, although they did not differ significantly. Interviewee 1 described it as a commitment to implementing several digital initiatives and as a building block in project management or project steering. The different phases herein are outlined as Minimum Viable Products (MVP), inspired by software delivery. Further, the interviewee stated that Agile methods and MVP go hand in hand.

Interviewee 4 described it as: “A roadmap to start achieving a certain goal, within 3 or 5 years, and along the way, it is refreshed because you are in a living environment. You do have to maintain a certain roadmap, and you would have to refresh it regularly regardless”. Further, the interviewee acknowledged the structure that the roadmap entails.

Interviewee 6 reasoned for a digital roadmap that “It is a mix of milestones, of objectives, of phases, of activities, of steps within a process. (...) it is related to go and no-go decisions to governance meetings et cetera”. Furthermore, the interviewee added to having a high-level roadmap that the roadmap should also be seen at a lower level, where it would focus more precisely.

- *Strategic Vision and Direction*

This objective was generally viewed as necessary. Interviewee 1 claimed

that defining a strategic vision and direction is the most crucial issue and is the starting point before developing a digital roadmap. Interviewee 3 stood by its criticality and described the vision as the North Star to be achieved. In doing so, Interviewee 1 suggested that this objective should be moved up a level. Interviewee 4 explained that this objective is vital; *“Even more important than a digital roadmap.”* In doing so, the interviewee implied that defining a strategic vision and direction is critical and serves as an essential input to the digital roadmap by stating that: *“If you do not know where you want to go, how can you create a roadmap?”*. Interviewee 2 reasoned that going through a DT because the competitor is doing it is the wrong approach. With this, the interviewee confirmed the importance of this objective and added that it is de facto important. Interviewee 3 described the digital roadmap as the “how” and the strategic vision and direction as the “what”. Interviewee 6 confirmed the necessity by reasoning that this objective is the first thing that needs to be done. Interviewee 5 stated that with them, in general, this aspect is not sufficiently addressed, although the interviewee himself has an image of where they would like to head as a company. The interviewee conceived that this objective is essential.

– *Digital Maturity*

This objective was also generally received as important; every interviewee confirmed its importance. Interviewee 4 described it as *“The second thing you are going to do”* after developing the strategic vision and direction. In doing so, the interviewee provided some questions to be answered: *“What level are we at with the company? What level are we at internally? In terms of digital development: are we in a beginning phase? Are we already in an evolved phase? Are we one of the leaders in the industry?”*

Furthermore, the interviewee stated that assessing digital maturity and determining it is the basis for defining the subsequent actions, such as the digital roadmap. Interviewee 5 stood by this statement and reasoned that digital maturity partly drives the digital roadmap. Interviewee 2 confirmed the necessity of this objective and explained that some companies today cannot assess and develop digital maturity. The interviewee emphasized this and substantiated it by explaining that *“About 50% of companies use the term digital strategy, but just so to speak, replace the term IT strategy with digital strategy. That is, they have no notion of the difference between IT and Digital”*.

Interviewee 6 gave the notion of an internal review and the thinking that goes with it: *“By reviewing the resources and capabilities within and thinking about how ready you are in potentially integrating digital technologies and changing your way of working”*. Interviewee 3 also spoke of an internal assessment about approaching the concept of DT. Interviewee 1 spoke of a broader test about how digital the company precisely is, depending on the magnitude of the project. Interviewee 5 indicated the company-

and sector-dependent aspect of this objective and stated that the need for assessing digital maturity might vary from company to company.

– *Evaluate and Prioritize Digital Ideas*

This objective was also generally well-received. As Interviewee 4 put it: “*You cannot do everything at the same time; there is no such thing*”. Interviewee 2 clarified that it is impossible to do everything simultaneously due to a limited budget, adding that making decisions is inherent to a company’s strategy. Furthermore, the interviewee stated that only 30% of DT’s succeed and that the 70% failure is partly due to choices that are not aligned with the company’s strategy. Interviewee 1 stated that there is rarely a shortage of ideas. The interviewee added that the number of ideas automatically trigger a kind of prioritization exercise.

Furthermore, the interviewee stated that ideas sometimes come out of a kind of defense reflex from people who sense that their position is under pressure, which does not imply that the ideas are always wrong. Interviewee 3 stated that no idea should be shot down, especially in an initial phase. For the prioritization exercise, the interviewee suggested three aspects: the feasibility: “*What is possible?*”, the cost: “*What is the cost of it?*” and the business value: “*What is it going to bring in both directly and indirectly?*” The interviewee added that in the background, aspects such as the company’s strategy, marketing, capabilities internally and people’s skills still need to be considered.

Interviewee 5 described the need for a particular platform through which an organization can share ideas, bottom-up.

Interviewee 1 described using the MoSCoW method during a kind of brainstorming session to run the prioritization exercise. The MoSCoW method is used for prioritizing requirements for which it presents four categories [92]: “*Must have*”, “*Should have*”, “*Could have*”, “*Will not have*”, in which “*Must have*” contains the most crucial requirements and “*Will not have*” the requirements that will not be implemented.

Interviewee 4 stated that the prioritization exercise occurs at different levels, both strategic and operational. The interviewee clarified that at the operational level, short-term decisions are made that pick up easy wins that create operational value. On a strategic level, the interviewee stated that decision-making is more important due to this matter’s long-term nature. The interviewee added that prioritization happens at the governance level. Interviewee 6 explained that through an A4 paper with a specific template, different ideas are collected and presented to management, performing the prioritization exercise according to the current strategy. Interviewee 5 indicated that the prioritization exercise is done at the directional level.

– *Asses Capability and Compatibility of IS*

When asked about the importance of assessing the capacity and compatibility of information systems (IS), responses were more mixed but overall

quite positive. For example, Interviewee 2 believed that this is not a guarantee of success and that reviewing outside technologies, which are not yet in-house, is necessary on top of the internal review of the company's information systems. To support this, the interviewee stated that *"If you see how many start-ups are operating today (...) and are all coming up with new, shattering ideas. If you do not put those on the radar screen with them, you will continue building on your own, old, sometimes rusty IT environment. The disruptive aspect of DT demands that you discard what you have today. Only if you really have to, and replace that with new technologies"*. To this, he added that in terms of a digital strategy, it is essential to include the rapid evolution of technologies in the exercises: *"That you do not limit yourself to your own capabilities"*.

Interviewee 4 noted that analyzing information systems is not sufficient; analyzing current business processes is also necessary. The interviewee substantiated by stating that businesses should always be involved and that the ultimate goal of a DT is to improve the business. The interviewee reasons: *"The outcome, or the profit or the value, is in the business. That is what you have to do it for"*. By doing so, the interviewee emphasized the business perspective that should also be captured in the assessment. The interviewee also proposed an expansion of this objective regarding the business perspective: *"Otherwise you get a one-sided IT story in which nobody wants to participate"*.

Interviewee 3 stated that this objective takes place in the back-end regarding technology. In doing so, the interviewee indicated that centralized information is an objective of DT. Interviewee 5 indicated the importance of knowledge regarding their infrastructure. To this, the interviewee added that it should be up-to-date as this will indicate further directions.

Interviewee 1 reasoned that this objective would not be essential for every project, that it is project dependent. A strong focus on this objective would then occur in DT projects where insights are gained from data. Here, the interviewee made the distinction between data-oriented projects and customer-oriented projects, including customer-facing. Furthermore, the interviewee indicated that the order of magnitude of a company indicates the extent to which this assessment would be necessary. The interviewee concluded by stating that *"When it comes to what in my experience is DT, it is less important, but it is indeed more likely to be on the agenda at larger companies"*.

Interviewee 6 indicated that the assessment forms through a weekly interaction between the IT department and senior management. These parties review whether current systems can support the new changes brought about by DT.

- Develop Agile Mindset

When interviewees were asked if developing an agile mindset was important, the answers were generally affirmative, although the meaning of this

objective ranged from project delivery to the overall agility of an organization. Interviewee 2 indicated that “agile” is a broad term and explained that *“Agile actually means that you can change very regularly, that you are responsive.”* Here, the interviewee added an example of the ability to anticipate a competitor’s price drop quickly and whether the systems allow it. Interviewee 1; Interviewee 3 spoke of the benefits of working Agile instead of the traditional waterfall method. In doing so, Interviewee 2 explained that Agile allows for faster response to change and stated that this is *“So crucial today as well”*. Interviewee 1 indicated that, from his own experience, an Agile method could produce better results than a waterfall method. In doing so, the interviewee mentioned using the Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) as an Agile method. Furthermore, he noted that the focus of Agile is more on the way of thinking than the tools for it. Interviewee 4 stated that they must be agile nowadays since they are constantly evolving. The interviewee concluded this by stating that *“If you are not agile, you fall behind.”*

Interviewee 6 stated that it is both a new way of thinking and an approach in project development. Further, the interviewee noted the connection to developing and assessing digital maturity, asserting that before having to be Agile, the digital maturity assessment reflects the extent to which the organization needs to develop an agile mindset. *“In certain cases, it really depends on case by case, for some organizations”*. Here, the interviewee added that it does not necessarily make sense and that the situation of the company and the outcome of the digital maturity assessment should be taken into account before going deeper into an agile mindset. Furthermore, the interviewee saw overlap with a further objective; Develop Digital Skillset and Mindset, and positioned this objective as a predominant concept.

– Develop and Increase Dynamic Capability

This objective was generally received with confusion. In doing so, five out of six interviewees indicated that they did not immediately understand what exactly was meant by this objective. For example, Interviewee 5 indicated to go straight to the explanation of this objective. Interviewee 6 indicated he was unsure what was meant and expressed confusion. Interviewee 3 also had some doubt about its meaning and saw potential confusion for future interviews. Interviewee 1; Interviewee 2 immediately linked agile, discussed in the previous objective. Interviewee 1 found this objective as not essential but thought it was worth to be considered. The interviewee followed this up with the following statement: *“If you are going to provide everything in-house, so the people who know something about digital transformation, the people who know something about real IT, the people who know something about change management, for example, you are going to incur many costs to find those people to start training, to start integrating into your business”*.

In doing so, the interviewee indicated that this objective could be satisfied by consultancy by incorporating dynamics in this way. Furthermore, the interviewee spoke of a possible bias towards this objective due to his background as a consultant.

Interviewee 4 expressed the link to the digital roadmap and stated that, in order to stay on this digital roadmap, a dynamic approach must be taken. The interviewee also indicated the need for this objective. He stated that there certainly is a need to be dynamic due to uncertainty in the future. Interviewee 2 opened with the statement: “*What is the difference between agile and dynamic? To me, it is the same thing*”. The interviewee followed this up by confirming that a company needs to evolve with its environment in today’s context. On the other hand, the interviewee indicated that the evolution must be robust, secure and GDPR compliant: “*There is a balance to be found between the agile and the dynamic, of course. You do have to make sure that it always remains robust and secure*”.

Interviewee 3 stated that dynamic capability for him could be two things. On the one hand, being flexible in tapping into the right people to implement DT, and on the other hand, being dynamic in operation to adjust pricing, for example. The interviewee concluded by stating that a one-sided interpretation of this objective is difficult.

Interviewee 5 indicated that simply being dynamic concerning the company’s resource base is not necessarily crucial. Before doing a reallocation of resources, the interviewee considered that a rebalancing of resources should be done that allows for resources to be used more efficiently. The interviewee supported this with an example in which he reasoned that allocating resources to tasks that can be solved by digitalization is not the solution. In doing so, he emphasized modifying the resource base, not necessarily expanding it.

– Assess Risk and Technology Appetite

This objective was generally well-received. As Interviewee 2 briefly reasoned by stating that this is typically one of the necessary aspects in such model. Interviewee 1 explained how that appetite for risk and technology plays a greater or lesser role according to the phases in a project. The early phases are driven by risk and by the openness of an organization. Further phases in implementation and a later part in change management count more often on risk aversion and restraint. The interviewee added that this reluctance manifests itself when there is a lack of framing, a lack of understanding regarding a DT project.

Interviewee 4 reasoned that organizations must be open to the “*Discovery in the Digital World*”. Further, the interviewee noted: “You have to have that mindset to dare to take risks and keep taking them. You also have to keep in mind that sometimes it can be a trigger and not every risky decision is a success.”

To this he added that: “*Even if it is a fail, you are going to learn from it, because then you know you should not be heading in that direction as*

a company.” He also reached back to the importance of making proofs of concepts in order to take risk.

Interviewee 3 linked to risk and security. For example, the interviewee illustrated the conversion of an old local mainframe to the cloud, which involves the risk of information loss.

Interviewee 5 reasoned that this would have to do with warming up the people in the organization regarding what innovation or digitization could potentially entail. The interviewee supported this with the following example: “*How do we do that today? Usually, we hold sessions every six months. That is a kind of internal event and there we try to put forward some topics from IT*”. To this, he added that appetite is necessary, “*Otherwise there is little sense in it*”.

Interviewee 6 explained by using an example in which students have to deal with several learning tools. Here they ran the risk of overlap with existing tools when a new learning tool was made available. This risk manifested itself in the context of confusion when offering a new learning tool when an existing learning tool already offered the same functionality. “*So this is an example where you assess risk. It is the, you might say, the confusion or the overlapping risk of new technology*”. The interviewee further stated that this assessment of risk is done on an ad hoc basis. He also mentioned some other elements of this assessment: “*Where the data is located and stored. Is it in our systems, or is it elsewhere? What is the risk of losing data? What is the risk of getting under a cyber-attack, if it is beyond our scope?*”

– Sense Disruption and Change in the Market

When interviewees were asked to assess this objective in terms of importance, the responses were again positive. Interviewee 1 did indicate that the importance appeared to depend on the perspective. He stated that in consultancy, one should know what is going on in the market and where disruptions are taking place. As a counter-example, the interviewee mentioned the financial sector, with its customer-facing aspect, as disruptive. He indicated the following regarding the disruptive aspect in the financial sector: “*But other than showing that to your customers (...) I do not really see much point in that*”. Furthermore, the interviewee situated this objective with the digital roadmap.

Interviewee 4 also situated this objective with the digital roadmap and indicated that this determines the refreshment of the digital roadmap. However, the interviewee made it clear that this is not the only thing that determines the refreshment. He also indicated the importance of this objective by stating that: “*If you have disruption in the market, or the market is evolving, then you have to evolve with it*”. He added the positioning of the company by stating that if a company wants to be the market leader in its industry or market, it must be able to sense disruptions and changes more quickly. Here the interviewee also referred back to the openness meant in the last objective: “*Back with that openness; you*

have to be open to changes. Once you are open for that, you will also be able to sense more quickly in certain markets which evolution is important for the company and how we are going to introduce and develop them within our company”.

Interviewee 2 indicated the importance of business relevance and clarified that a company must offer a counter-move in response to competition. Interviewee 3 linked back to DT drivers and reasoned that change in customers and competitors is one of the drivers of DT. Interviewee 5 also indicated the importance of this objective and described the question to be answered: *“What can we start using disruptive technology for that will make us relevant in 100 years?”* Furthermore, the interviewee stated that every sector should take note of changes in the market.

Interviewee 6 agreed with identifying this objective and the role it plays in the global picture. However, the interviewee did not fully agree with the position of the objective. He stated that along with the objective *Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies*; this objective relates more to assessing the environment and context. He explained: *“For me, there is more, and I would have exactly the same comment for trends and emerging technologies. [Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies] is more about the assessment of the environment and the context”.* In this, he distinguishes two perspectives: inside and outside.

– *Develop and Reconfigure Business and IT Resources*

This objective was perceived more or less positively, nevertheless with some concerns. Interviewee 3 found this objective difficult to understand and situated the reconfiguration towards support. He further suggested that this objective should be clarified. Interviewee 2 stated that if 70% of DT’s fail, it is usually not about IT. For this, he reached back to the operating model and diamond of change [93], which states that any organizational system is built by four main components: People, Task, Structure and Technology. In doing so, he made the following comment, when DT then manifests itself: *“Then it is about how employees can participate in that new way of working and it is about the human aspects. Those are generally covered a little too little in the model”.*

Further, he stood by this statement, explaining that: *“50% of employees do not see any immediate benefits, from a digital transformation, for their job. Surely this is important. One-third of the employees do not feel involved in a digital transformation, where actually 80% would like to participate in a digital transformation”.*

The interviewee concluded this by reasoning that if the aspects concerning organizational change are not considered, the DT will ultimately lead to failure. To this, he added that flanking measures are often needed for a theoretical concept to ensure that everyone implementing the strategy can follow through and that *“All aspects of the business, processes, organizations, skills, governance, culture, are aligned accordingly”.*

Interviewee 5 indicated that he was unsure if this objective should be included and stated that the infrastructure to accomplish this will quickly be at its limit. Interviewee 1 explained that this is an aspect where DT projects blow up negatively. He validated this by stating that a defined strategy and roadmap is often not feasible from a technical standpoint due to poor alignment with the IT side. To achieve this alignment, he offered the solution of involving existing resources in the digital roadmap or strengthening the IT department's capacity, if necessary, with resources that are not yet present in the organization. Here, as an additional aspect, he indicated that a dynamic and collaborative IT department in order to be able to reconfigure quickly is of great importance.

Interviewee 4 viewed this objective as something that should be kept in mind continuously. He indicated that the necessary business resources might change today in the company, within three or five years, due to the strategy being subject to constant evolution. He concluded this by stating that *"You have to start developing different skills than the ones we have today"* and that *"If you ever want to start implementing that strategy, at certain times you will need different types of resources than you need today"*.

Interviewee 6 linked this objective and the objective Assess Capability and Compatibility of IS. In doing so, he reasoned that if the assessment of the capability and compatibility of IS indicates that there are misalignment or that there is room for improvement, that this assessment indicates whether or not the reconfiguration of business and IT resources is necessary. To assist this, he explained: *"If you perform the assessments of the capability and the compatibility of IT and the result is: it is fully compatible and we recently invested in the latest open and interoperable systems, for example. Then you would necessarily conclude that the reconfiguration of your IT resources is, for example, not necessarily needed, right? I would see the development and the reconfiguration of IT as a potential action to perform if your assessment has turned out to be not so optimal"*.

- Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies This objective was also predominantly well received by the interviewees. Although Interviewee 1 gave the notion of overlap with Sense Disruption and Change in the Market: *"I see a fair amount of overlap with [Sense Disruption and Change in the Market]. (...) I think that it is similar in how I have to look at it."* Again, he indicated that he would position this objective at the inception phase, at the digital roadmap.

Interviewee 4 stated that when a company is at the end of an evolutionary cycle, it will need to renew itself. He added that sometimes the only way to move forward is to be very disruptive: *"At some point, you have to go so disruptive, you have to go up a gear in the market, and this maturity of your skills and IT skills, and digital skills, which by the way is not only IT. Sometimes the only way to seriously move forward is to go very disruptive"*

and look at it like: we are in a certain technology that has reached the end of its rope”.

He added that going along with the new emerging technologies and evolving and anticipating them is the logical next step. Finally, he indicated that the “When” is vital regarding the right time to be disruptive. He concluded this objective with the following statements: *“When is the right moment to start working disruptively? Moreover, do we know if we are going to work disruptively, whether that will contribute value to the company?”*

Interviewee 2 opined that it does not mean that an organization should de facto seize upon trends and emerging technologies, just because the competition is doing it. Nevertheless, it is and remains very important to look at what the competition is doing. Also, seizing on these trends and these emerging technologies must fit within one’s own goals, within one’s strategy. He further stated that it remains an own evaluation since the company either considers something necessary or not. Regarding the investments involved, the interviewee explained that there might be other priorities beyond simply participating in a trend. He further explained, by taking Robotic Process Automation (RPA) as an example. He indicated that one out of five RPA projects reaches an acceptable maturity level; four out of five do not. With this, he demonstrated that: *”Just joining for fun, because the competitors are doing it, that is not an option.”* He closed by stating that seizing upon trends and emerging technologies will only be successful if it fits with the strategy and if it is done thoroughly and accurately.

Interviewee 6 stated that it is essential to have a strategic view of the market. He also indicated that this strategic view situates from the outside perspective. Interviewee 5 grasped back to the infrastructure to hand at the company in question. The interviewee again reiterated that before the infrastructure is not brought up-to-date, this objective would not yet be addressed. With this, he linked with the previous objective, Develop and Reconfigure Business Resources and IT Resources. Furthermore, Interviewee 3 stated that different velocities could be found in them depending on the sectors.

- *Branch Two*

- Evaluate Financial Ability

For the second branch of the model, only one objective is present. This objective was also perceived as important by the interviewees. Interviewee 1 said this was a valid objective and added that it is often underestimated in terms of time spent evaluating financial capability. He added that a company’s financial strength to support DT should be sufficient even if it goes worse than expected. To conclude, he gave a 7/10 score to importance and 9/10 to overall underestimation.

Interviewee 4 indicated that he indeed considered this objective important in the context of a digital strategy. He also felt that the model should mention financial capability together with people capability: “*You have to have the dollars as well, but the people are also crucial. If you do not have the people available, you cannot get anywhere either*”. Interviewee 2 indicated that this objective is de facto important.

Interviewee 3 referred to the business case of which financial capability is a component. He also indicated that the financial dimension is one of the drivers for DT. For this objective, he made it clear that it is crucial to look at this from two perspectives. On the one hand, whether the budget is there and on the other hand whether it is profitable to implement. As an example, this interviewee gave the conversion of a company to the cloud. He also situated opportunity costs and initial introduction costs under this objective as well. He also further pointed out overlap, at least in his perspective; “*Financial Ability and Change in Value Creation. We always take these two jointly*”.

Interviewee 6 also indicated that the business case for DT projects should be made. The board of directors needs to be shown the costs associated with the DT projects and the revenues. These returns are not necessarily in terms of financial returns. It should also be in terms of hours saved, in terms of efficiency.

Interviewee 5 indicated the evidentiary nature of this objective. Based on a yearly defined budget and financial control, the deviations from the foreseen budget are tracked, and, depending on the situation, an additional budget is provided. As an example of a deviation, he mentioned the COVID-19 pandemic.

- *Branch Three*

- Identify Structural Changes

This objective was also generally found to be important. Interviewee 1 reasoned that part of prioritizing digital ideas includes identifying structural changes. He also gave attention to the hard-skills part, the technical capability needed to execute DT projects. He added that large companies that have been around for a long time are more likely to suffer because structural aversion concerning DT manifests itself. This aversion implies the implementation of a cultural mindset change. He also indicated that this type of change is often more difficult than tapping into resources or building systems and the like. He concluded by saying that when a DT project goes wrong, this error is located in the cultural mindset rather than in the technical difficulty of the project.

Interviewee 4 linked the digital maturity phase of a company. If a company is in a particular maturity phase, it may be possible to implement the DT with the current organizational structure. If the company wants to achieve higher maturity to undertake the DT, it will prove necessary to assess the organizational structure. In this assessment, the key questions

to be answered are: *“Is the current organizational set-up still the right organizational set-up to start accomplishing DT in the future? What is the best structure to start introducing that digital world into the company?”*

At the same time, he also linked here with the business objectives present by mentioning that a digital strategy is a means to achieve the business objectives. He also saw the organizational structure as a means to achieve the business objectives.

Interviewee 2 opened by stating that this is not just important but vital. For this, too, he reached back to the operating model, mentioning several aspects to be considered: *“In which manner are we going to redesign the processes, in which manner are we going to adapt the organization, the roles, the competencies? In which manner are we going to organize the governance, the dashboards we use, the KPI’s we use to pilot the development of the process in the right direction? In what manner are we going to reframe the culture, how our employees work together to operationalize that process. And then lastly, deploy the IT resources to enable that process”*.

He also mentioned the five different axes of the operating model, as explained in Section 4.4. In doing so, he explained that these components are interrelated and that if one component shifts, the others must shift with it; *“If you do not do that, for instance, you are not going to look at the organization, then it will not work. Then the change is not sustainable”*. Interviewee 3 viewed a DT as a structural change in itself. He explained that these structural changes could appear very disruptive on the one hand or be implemented in parallel. This parallel implementation takes care of adopting, for example, a new system in the sense that it is still possible to alternate between the old system and the new system before the switch is final.

He further proposed modifying this objective regarding the innate nature of a structural change to DT. In the sense that the nature of the structural change needs to be determined: *“Are you really heading for a big bang, or are you going to work gradually?”* He explained that in practice, this is a point of discussion and very challenging to determine.

Interviewee 5 explained that staff readiness is necessary to enable smooth structural changes. Interviewee 6 tried to approach a holistic picture and positioned this objective after defining the vision (the strategic intent) and assessing the digital maturity (strategic analysis). According to the interviewee, a combination of the strategic intent and strategic analysis outcomes would allow an organization or company to be better positioned to identify these structural changes. After a brief explanation of the different leaf-level objectives presented in Branch Three, he indicated that he did not wholly agree that this is related to identifying structural changes. He stated that: *“It is not really about identifying structural changes, it is more about bringing the necessary, the required bricks in order to identify*

the changes, so here I do not see the list of initiatives and changes. I see more the ingredients to make sure that this will happen”.

He clarified that he considers this branch to be more an ingredient list with the right internal ingredients to ensure a smooth DT. He further indicated that the compatibility, the interoperability of IS systems also belongs under structural changes. He also mentioned that tapping into resources belongs under this branch, in the sense that these resources are needed to close the gap brought about by a potential structural change.

After a brief recap of this information, he continued regarding this branch, mentioning one more possible adjustment. According to the interviewee, this missing aspect links the DT agenda and existing processes or strategies. He reasoned that an alignment between an organization’s digital initiatives, strategies and operating model is necessary to enable integration, leading to an integrated DTS.

– Foster Digital Skillset and Mindset

The interviewees also found the importance of this objective. Interviewee 2 stated that this is de facto important and is self-evident. Interviewee 3 reasoned that the digital skillset and mindset is always an underlying pillar. He also sees this as a strategic workforce. Furthermore, he indicated that entire trajectories are set up to demonstrate the importance of changes in the market and how to deal with them for DT projects. Interviewee 5 stated that investing in systems that people do not use due to a lack of knowledge or framing would be a waste. For the company in question, he indicated using a scorecard as an evaluation form that lists the different skills needed and goals to be achieved for each staff member individually.

Interviewee 4 also indicated that both business and IT should be on board with the necessary digital skills necessary now and within five years. The question that arises here is: *“How can we start introducing them into our business?”* Here he added that this allows for determining how the people present in the company need to start transforming themselves towards the new digital skills needed. *“In order to start doing that, you first have to have that mindset. Otherwise, you cannot start implementing all those other things. That is the key”.* With this, he emphasized the importance of this objective.

Interviewee 1 indicated that the motivation to work with DT in a company is not always there, and thus promoting the digital skillset and mindset is always an area of concern. He stated that due to the magnitude of a company, implications could occur regarding creating such a mindset. He elaborated that the lower in the company hierarchy, the more difficult this becomes. He added that the people in a higher position in the corporate hierarchy usually come up with the strategic vision and are concerned with market trends and disruption, but that the vision is often unclear to the people on the shop floor. He reasoned that these people would execute the DT and indicated that that makes this objective crucial. He

also pointed out the danger of dissonance among staff, in that there is no connection between the staff and higher management and as a result, the digital mindset is missing. This dissonance could lead to complications in the future.

Interviewee 6 indicated that digital skillset and mindset are important, but also that resources to close the gap as previously as explained in Section 4.9.1 are necessary; otherwise, this gap will not be closed.

- Foster Transformational Leadership Again, interviewees responded positively in terms of importance. As Interviewee 4 put it concisely: “*That is a must-have, concise answer*”. Interviewee 5 also stated it concisely: “*Absolutely. Those have to set a good example, lead by example*”.

Interviewee 1 reasoned that: “*Because whatever the leader does, the followers will likely adopt*”. Nevertheless, he expressed that this is not always the case, and the followers may display self-defense. He also made it clear that if a leader does not have the desired mindset, the followers will certainly not be willing to transform. He also indicated that in terms of transformational leadership, it could also be sufficient for senior management in a team to show commitment to motivate and push the team along in the direction that the strategy has set. The interviewee viewed transformational leadership as someone who will work out the strategy, as a sort of “*Elon Musk figure*”.

Interviewee 2 indicated that this objective is de facto important. To support this, he cited some figures. He reasoned that about four out of ten managers declare to have no experience or insufficient training in DT. He added that managers admit that there is a leadership deficit and that this is one reason why digital initiatives fail. He mentioned that this is evident from a study conducted by Binder Dijker Otte (BDO) in 2020.

Interviewee 3 stated that leadership drives a company’s vision: “*No vision is no [digital transformation], all your pillars too*”. He then reasoned that everything starts with a good strategy driven by leadership. He further stated that once the DT is underway, that the support from senior management is of high importance, as they would represent the “*Active Advocates*” of the transformation.

Interviewee 6 also indicated the importance of top-bottom support to obtain solid support from the hierarchy.

- Establish a DT Unit

This objective was received critically by each interviewee, in the sense that isolating a DT unit does not appear to be optimal. Interviewee 4 opened by saying that the importance of this objective depends on the corporate culture. In a separate unit, the interviewee reasoned that the work to be performed is pushed in a kind of top-down or drill-down manner, which can have detrimental effects on motivation. Furthermore, he explained: “*That in case of DT it is better to have the business structure carry DT itself, to which the people belong. Then you are going to be able to work*

more constructively. When people are open to those things, you are going to be able to accomplish more”.

After this, he elaborated on the lack of support from the roles that need to implement a DT, leading to a more complicated relationship in the DT story. As a best practice, he suggested that if an organization decides to put down a DT unit, it is composed of people from every function. These people represent the function representatives. According to the interviewee, this could lead to more support within the functions. This composition allows the function representatives to bring the decision-making process to the table at their respective functions. He further clarified that this loss of support manifests when the people with an operational role are not in touch with the people who determine the strategy. Interviewee 2 expressed that this objective always brings about a very challenging discussion. He indicated that half of the companies have the ambition to set up a DT unit. To this, he added: *“But, that is the same as quality: from the moment you make a certain cell responsible for this, the others think that it is no longer their concern, and therefore they cannot contribute to it”.*

He further suggested that the model should recommend a DT unit as a competency group within an organization. Since, according to the interviewee, responsibility should not be taken away from those with operational responsibility. According to him, a DT Unit with full responsibility regarding DT would impede progress. He then followed up on this by indicating that: *“Often the risk here is that we set up a DT unit and voila, we are finished. They will push the change. That will never work”.*

Interviewee 3 also indicated that establishing a DT unit may be relevant in some cases, usually at large companies. He further explained that in practice, a center of excellence is set up. According to the interviewee, this should be seen as a group of people who centrally lead the DT and ensure that it is well thought out towards the various departments within a company. According to the interviewee, this should be in the form of specific guidelines to adhere to. He concluded by stating that this is a specific issue and perhaps less important in the bigger picture.

Interviewee 1 found that a DT unit as a focused task force has its advantages, but that this is not always a success story. Here he spoke of a barrier when each member of the task force wants their input followed up. He further spoke that he feels a cross-functional task force with members from different departments or functions within the company is best for the DT to succeed. This interviewee also mentioned the support that can be created in this manner. He then indicated that these task force members should involve the other members of their department or function in the DT.

Interviewee 5 indicated the company-specific regarding the need to establish a DT unit, or in the interviewee’s words, a DT office. He reasoned

that a transversal department consisting of a mix of business and IT people are needed in one organization. This department can be put down since the right people are already in the business. The creation of this department would then lead to an internal reorganization. The DT would be at each business unit level or driven by an IT department in the other organization. He concluded by stating that proper governance is imperative.

- *Branch Four*

- Identify Possible Changes

This objective was also generally perceived as necessary. Interviewee 2 indicated the importance of this objective by reasoning that this was ultimately the beginning of his discussion. He stated that: “*There has to be focused in the function of the strategy. Value creation is obviously the focus of the strategy*”. By which he positions value creation centrally in his discussion. According to the interviewee, this value creation can be in terms of customer focus, product leadership, or operational excellence: “*Without making that exercise of value creation, you should not get started*”.

Interviewee 6 also indicated the importance of this objective, stating: “*That is the overall goal of it all, right?*” Interviewee 4 explained that to achieve the digital strategy, the organization must ensure that value creation shifts in a favorable direction. He indicated that the more efficient an organization operates, the more value it creates and the more meaningful the work becomes for the people present in the organization. Furthermore, he again indicated the openness towards DT and the culture associated with it.

Interviewee 5 linked this objective and the relevance of an organization. According to the interviewee, this includes, for example, offering added value to the end-user and deploying personnel more efficiently.

Interviewee 3 found that this objective is strongly related to the financial ability of an organization. With this objective, he looked at the two aspects that come into play in DT: operational efficiency and top revenue growth. He mentioned the flexibility that the DT project brings and the lower associated costs with operational efficiency. According to the interviewee, top revenue growth is the most important; this is the margin to be viewed and how an organization can increase it.

Interviewee 1 stated that this objective is primarily in the early stages of a DT process. Furthermore, he also mentioned that this can be important to determine the drivers of DT: “*Why are you doing it and why do you necessarily want to digitalize now?*” He also said that it is vital to link the objective back to the business strategy.

- Follow, Analyze and Anticipate Customer Behaviour

This objective was also generally well-received as Interviewee 4 replied: “*Yes, wholeheartedly yes. You have to understand your customer*”. Interviewee 2 reasoned: “*Without the customers, the company would not exist*”.

Interviewee 5 also indicated that these are hugely important issues. Interviewee 1 approached the objective in the context of a project and reasoned that the importance here depends on the type of project. Here, he distinguished projects to increase internal efficiency, reasoning that the customer is not always the end customer, but it is also whom DT projects are done for, such as the staff. Also, in the context of the customer as the end customer, he argued that when anticipating customer behavior, it is essential to assess the return to the organization: *“Suppose your customers become 5 [percent] happier, but your logistics department becomes 40 [percent] unhappier (...) what you have to ask yourself then is: what is the return for our organization in the end?”* In doing so, he stated that in this view, the manager must make considerations. He added that it is also essential to demonstrate some independence, as customers often think in the short term while an organization builds for the long term.

Interviewee 2 explained that nowadays, there are many exercises around outside-in, customer journeys, and design thinking: *“To start defining from the customer’s point of view much better how the company can generate value through the relationship with the customer, over the years. Moreover, to me, that seems to be the ultimate goal of the exercise.”* Unlike Interviewee 1, this interviewee reasoned that DT could not be purely about improving internal operations. He concluded that: *“The finality lies with the customer who pays for it, or not”*. Interviewee 6 connected this objective with customer experience, explaining that through, for example, the buying experience or the transaction experience, value can be generated for the customer.

– Identify Processes that can be Enhanced by Digital Technology

This objective was also found to be generally important among the interviewees. Interviewee 5 described how processes are streamlined within the organization in question by monitoring, analyzing and anticipating customer behavior, in this case, student behavior. For example, he indicated that here a single tool to manage end-to-end processes, from the choice of a thesis topic to the defense of the thesis, is in use. Interviewee 4 stated that there is no point in introducing digital technology for the sake of digital technology. He argued that before introducing digital technologies, it is clear that an organization must first identify these processes; *“So for what processes does it make sense?”* He reasoned: *“Automating just to automate will not move you forward”*.

Interviewee 2 stuck to his operating model: *“The processes, activities, business-wise, are at the center of any discussion because they ensure that the customer experience, their touchpoint with the customer, is operationalized. Thus, that is also the focus of any exercise around DT”*. Interviewee 3 reasoned that the objective is undoubtedly part of the required capabilities. He gave the example of replacing *“old-fashioned ways”* such as switching from paperwork to digital at an accounting firm. However, Interviewee 1 believed that this objective corresponds to the

objective “*Identify Possible Changes in Value Creation and Operational Efficiency*”. He indicated that he gave this objective slightly less value: “*Because I think you have to keep thinking broader than just: what process can I improve?*” Furthermore, he indicated the risk of tunnel vision: “*That you should not only start looking at processes, but then you should involve the bigger picture*”. He was concerned that this could potentially be the case with this objective. As a demonstrative example, he described a DT project for recruitment where the process and the “*whole story*” of recruitment should be improved.

– Establish Synergy between Digital and Traditional Offerings

Interviewee 2; Interviewee 4 argued that establishing synergy between digital and traditional offerings is not a choice. As Interviewee 4 stated: “*I do not think you have a choice. If you do not establish synergy, you are going to live in two separate worlds. And then you are not moving forward either*”. Interviewee 2 responded: “*It is not one or the other; it is one and the other. [An organization] should not throw the value of the traditional processes away*”. Interviewee 4 added to his statement that there is a necessity to look at the traditional set-ups and how the digital opportunities can support them to operate more effectively. He reasoned that conflict situations arise when an organization disconnects the traditional set-ups from the digital opportunities. To this, he added that an organization should avoid these conflict situations.

Additionally, he also indicated that if this conflict situation occurs, then those employed in the traditional set-up will no longer be open to DT. He reiterated the need to work cooperatively, which, according to the interviewee, will allow for more to be achieved. He followed this up with the following statement: “*You are going to see much faster: which processes are candidates to be digitalized and which processes do not make sense? In fact, for which ones is it wasted. The synergy will reinforce that as well. As a result, the company is also going to improve in terms of operational activities*”.

Interviewee 6 indicated that the objective is okay, although he reasoned that there might be a section missing here regarding the creation of value by providing a new type of service or adding an add-on to the business model. He mentioned: “*By changing your business model, so you may create value by creating a new type of activity. Think about potential platforms that we may launch, digital platforms that will help you to create additional revenue*”.

Moreover, he clarified what creates the delivery of new services or the addition of an add-on to the business model: “*With purely transformative and disruptive opportunities, which are not necessarily in line with the traditional ones. So something that is created thanks to the digital technologies fully*”. He further indicated that this should be incorporated to clarify this objective.

Interviewee 5 gave as an example the digital signing of contracts through a lightweight app through which the traditional process of signing is executed digitally. “*So if you are going to look at that traditional process like that and then throw that digital flavor over it so that you get optimization (...) then that is certainly an essential one*”.

Interviewee 3 claimed that traditional and digital offerings would be running in parallel by default. He went on to state that the strategy of both must be aligned. For example, he gave a real estate agency where transactional, non-value-added tasks such as requesting soil tests would be steered towards “*the digital*” while the advice part would most likely “*still happen in an office*”.

Interviewee 1 gave the example of the synergy present at Coolblue, which in current times pursues a brick-and-mortar strategy in addition to its online webshop: “*That is also why you see that such a Coolblue, for example, pursues a huge brick-and-mortar strategy, whereas they initially operated online. Because ultimately, people still want to see: what does that TV look like? What do I have? Moreover, that the whole buying process can remain online*”. He further stated that this objective “*has to be taken into account by all means*”.

- *Issues in General*

Here, we will focus on the responses to the question of whether the respondents think that the model is complete or not. If this question was answered negatively by the interviewee, they were asked if they could think of a solution. This section also mentions the aspects that came up during the interview that were not directly relevant to the objective in question. This section is organized based on the addressed overarching themes. The identified themes are: the content of strategic objectives, the structure of the model, and the practicality of the model.

- Content of the Model

In what follows, we will describe the aspects mentioned by the interviewees concerning the content of strategic objectives.

For example, Interviewee 1 answered that there are many pertinent aspects in the model. He stated that if someone made a correlation prediction of the model through statistical methods, the result would indicate that there are “*many elements*” present in the model that are critical for DT. Interviewee 4 indicated that he found the model “*quite complete*”. However, he found certain parts missing, such as the people aspect belonging to the financial aspect, as explained earlier. When asked if anything else was missing from the model, this interviewee replied that he found it “*mostly clear*”. He indicated that he thought the maturity stage of the business was very important and added: “*Depending on the maturity of your business, you are going to have to do more or fewer steps*”. When

the interviewer asked the interviewee if it was mainly related to governance, he indicated that this is one of the aspects and that an assessment of the governance model, which may or may not be in place, is necessary. Interviewee 2 expressed concern, explaining that he initially “misses a little bit of the business strategy”, being that: “The model here is sort of indicating that a DTS is the [ultimate] goal. It is a means to another end, that is, the business objectives, which is the business strategy”. Also, he indicated that he might have been misled as a consequence: “Purely (...) by the representation of the model”. Interviewee 2 indicated that although this model presents many theoretical building blocks that are correct, he considers the full scope: *“Is the organization ready for a [digital] transformation? How am I going to assess that my company can handle the digital transformation? And what is my change strategy going to be? Throughout the next few years, to include my employees in the equation. Where is the starting point, and how far do I want to reach? Which individuals do I need to drop, dismiss à la limite? And what new competencies do I need to bring in?”*

He found this part insufficiently addressed, although he gave the notion of the presence of the objectives regarding transformational leadership and digital skillset. He also indicated that fundamental components were missing in terms of culture and governance. According to the interviewee, these would be necessary *“To correctly manage the to-be operating model, which DT enables”*. Furthermore, he also indicated *“missing the whole range of organizational change”*: He explained: *“If 70% of DTs fail, it is not due to the strategy, not to the digital components. It is entirely due, according to most studies, to the people component. The fact that there has not been any consideration of: in what way are we going to enthuse people? In what way are we going to reassure people that we will do the transformation with them? In what way are we going to ensure for those people that they are going to accomplish that new job, that they will accomplish it in a completely different way, in what way are we going to ensure that they will be able to do that? In what way are we going to support them as well?”*

The interviewee indicated that the model says *“many good things”* but that there are still many aspects not specified. In conclusion, he indicated: *“With the components listed here on this slide, you make, on slides, a pretty strategy. However, it will never work, unfortunately. Some crucial components are not mentioned here, mainly concerning the people side, the culture side. (...) For me, it is about the whole transformation, corporate, which [the model] does not include”*.

Interviewee 3 found that the main cornerstones are present in the model but indicated that it is not complete. One aspect he mentioned here is to *“Get inspired by external insights, to the benchmark, to how other customers or how the other competitors deal with this. That is something that I do not think you mentioned, but that is very important”*. Moreover,

he felt that the model was “75% right” and that: “*Everything you say is important too*”. He followed this up with: “*But I do not think everything is in there*”.

Interviewee 6 reasoned that the model is incomplete: *You could already understand that the model is not complete*”. Here he referred to the aspects he covered during the interview.

– Structure of the Model

Interviewee 6 gave the notion of, in his opinion, some issues. The first issue arose when dealing with Branch One of the model, as indicated earlier. Here he proposed two complementary perspectives: inside and outside perspective.

He considered the objectives Develop and Assess Digital Maturity and Develop and Increase Dynamic Capability to be something “*inside*” the organization. At the same time, in his view, Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies and Sense Disruption and Change in the Market are for him “*outside*” the organization. According to the interviewee, the inside view would be about an organization’s strengths, weaknesses and compatibility to execute DT. The outside view would be about the opportunities and threats outside the organization. He also recommended before embarking on the objective Evaluate and Prioritize Digital Ideas to do a kind of strategic marketwatch: “*Then, out of the digital maturity analysis and external watch analysis, I could derive (...) the evaluation and the prioritization of the digital ideas*”.

This strategic marketwatch would deal with the opportunities and threats outside the organization and obtain inspiration from other cases. With this marketwatch, the interviewee linked with the objectives Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies and Sense Disruption and Change in the Market, representing the marketwatch. To this, he added that this represents the outside view and should occur before anything is developed: “*For me, it is something that even before trying to develop something, you need to assess it*”. The interviewee also indicated that he positioned the people’s skillset and mindset in the organization from the inside view. He reasoned that the objective regarding digital maturity is a kind of “*digital health check*”, “*Which is only about the organization.*” Also, this interviewee situated Develop Agile Mindset as a sub-objective of Assess and Develop Digital Maturity, as explained earlier.

For Branch Three, Interviewee 6 indicated a flow of objectives, with objectives in Branch One such as Develop and Assess Digital Maturity, Strategic Vision and Direction, and the objectives from the aforementioned outside view positioned before Identify Structural Changes. He reasoned that meeting these objectives will enhance the organization’s ability to identify these structural changes. Interviewee 6 also indicated regarding the structure that he considers the objective Assessment of Capability and Compatibility of IS as a sub-objective of Assess and

Develop Digital Maturity. He explained that: “*If your current infrastructure is not compatible or ready to support the transformation, then it is a negative impact on the digital maturity assessment*”.

– Practicality of the Model

Interviewee 1 gave the notion of lack of order or sequence in the model. For example, he reasoned that he needed “*some moment*” to set the vision and strategic direction, for example: “*If I look at it now, it is more like a kind of consequence, after the [digital] roadmap, whereas I see that more like a kind of starting point*”. He said he “*did not immediately*” identify things that were lacking from the model in terms of content.

Interviewee 4 also commenced sequencing the objectives at some point in the interview. The interviewer pointed this out. To this, he responded: “*I do give an order to it because I think that is what is needed most of all*”. He emphasized that he found it necessary to indicate a particular flow to the model: “*It is just a network of activities now. I do not think the dependencies emerge very obviously. Because you can only perform certain things if other things have [already] been performed, that is very good in terms of content and as a concept, but you cannot just execute everything*”.

On this momentum, he continued, reasoning that while an organization can execute the objectives in parallel, it has to start somewhere: “*What should the company start with? What is the first step in this digital transformation strategy journey? What are the first aspects they need to focus on? Then what are the next aspects they need to focus on?*” To this, he continued by stating that these are the building blocks to develop the strategy. However, he wondered: “*Which building blocks then do we start with first?*” He also indicated that these aspects are highly critical to be developed.

Interviewee 3 expressed his biggest concern about the model; “*I think it is more of a checklist than an approach. That is my biggest concern*”. After this, he expressed the feeling of having one objective where he has to give his explanation “*at the very beginning of the process*” and then again “*at the very back*”. As an example, he gave the objective here: Follow, Analyze and Anticipate on Customer Behavior. He explained: “*I went all the way back at the end – that last question was follow, analyze and anticipate on customer behavior – yes, this is the very first thing you do*”. Further, he explained he did not fully understand why, for example, the objective Foster Transformational Leadership is a requirement to Identify Structural Change.

As a solution to this, he would create a checklist of the objectives, in which the objectives represent high-level key milestones for DT. Still, he indicated that he thought the model was robust: “*I think it is firm. I say in practice, there are some other things. Moreover, there is no sequence to it*”. Furthermore, he indicated that he did not see how the DTS should be sustained and iterated on. “*There are also many steps associated with*

it that you then also have to do to follow it up, to adjust, to test. [The model] does not mention all of that either”.

As indicated by Interviewee 1; Interviewee 4, Interviewee 6 also indicated to prefer a sequential view. On the one hand, he agreed that the elements present were interesting. On the other hand, he reasoned: *“But it does not necessarily (...) match the picture that I have of [digital transformation] and it is also due to the fact that I have a more sequential view on digital transformation”*. Incidentally, he added that: *“I would really prefer going into a more sequential view because it brings much more insights than just a mind map”*. The interviewee further mentions that he is *“not at ease and comfortable”* with *“the logic by which those different sub-concepts are related”*.

Interviewee 5 pointed to the evaluation of the digital roadmap and suggested that the progress of the digital roadmap should be included in the model. For this, he viewed the digital roadmap as something that needs to be re-assessed *“every so often”*: *“Because you are not going to make it in one session. You have to come back to it regularly”*.

C.2 Main Findings

Table C2 shows the main findings regarding the first branch of the model. The column **Importance** addresses the strengths regarding the objectives. These are the aspects that interviewees cited to support or explain the perceived importance of an objective. Weaknesses, shortcomings and proposals concerning an objective are described in the column Considerations to be made. This column displays the aspects interviewees cited regarding the content of an objective. The column also displays **considerations to be made** for each objective, aspects to be changed about the objective, or issues that arose during the interviews regarding the clarity and boundaries of objectives. The considerations to be made could serve as an input for future developments concerning the model.

Table C2: To be completed!!

Branch One	Importance	Considerations to be made
Develop a Digital Roadmap	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A digital roadmap helps structure projects; - A digital roadmap is the foundation of DT; - A digital roadmap is a building block in project management or project steering; - A digital roadmap is a roadmap towards a certain goal; - A digital roadmap is related to go and no-go decisions; - A digital roadmap is a substantial part of the business plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement not only a high-level digital roadmap but also at lower levels with a specific scope; - Regular refreshment due to a living environment; - Inspire the digital roadmap by software delivery and project management (through MVP and Agile methods); - Clearly define what the digital roadmap entails and how it can be drawn up.

Define Strategic Vision and Direction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly crucial as a starting point before developing a digital roadmap; - Serves as a crucial input to the digital roadmap; - Describes the “what” concerning DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specify this objective as the first step to be taken toward formulating a DTS.
Develop and Assess Digital Maturity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The assessment of digital maturity serves as a basis to determine further actions to be taken; - Drives the digital roadmap; - Determines the readiness of an organization to engage in DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Its importance depends on the magnitude of an organization; - Not every organization is capable of assessing and developing digital maturity; - The importance of this objective is company and sector-dependent.
Evaluate and Prioritize Digital Ideas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is impossible to implement all digital ideas at the same time; - Making decisions is inherent to a company’s strategy; - Failure comes in part from decision-making that is not aligned with an organization’s strategy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate and prioritize based on the feasibility, cost and business value of a digital idea; - Implement a platform to allow idea sharing and collection; - Present different ideas using a specific template to allow standardized and easy presentation; - Prioritize through use of the MoSCoW method; - The prioritization exercise takes place at both the strategic (long term) and operational level (short term).
Assess Capability and Compatibility of IS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The infrastructure of IS in place should be contemporary as it indicates further directions; - Strong emphasis on this objective in data-oriented DT; - Determines whether IS can support new changes brought about by DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not a guarantee of success as putting on the radar and reviewing out-house technologies and capabilities is also necessary (on top of an internal review of in-house technologies and capabilities); - Clarification of this objective is much needed as it intuitively is found to only concern technological aspects, not taking into account the broader context of IS; - The magnitude of a company determines the importance of this objective; - Assess through regular interaction with IT department and senior management; - This objective as a sub-objective of Assess and Develop Digital Maturity as incompatible infrastructure has a negative impact on digital maturity.
Develop Agile Mindset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to quickly anticipate on competition behavior; - Allows for faster response to change; - Crucial in a contemporary environment as to not fall behind among competition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set clear boundaries on this objective as it is both a new way of thinking and related to project development; - Digital maturity assessment outcome determines the extent to which an agile mindset should be maintained; - Foster digital skillset and mindset as an overarching objective.
Develop and Increase Dynamic Capability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A dynamic approach is needed to stay on the digital roadmap - Dynamic capability is needed to react or anticipate due to uncertainty in the future; - Need to evolve in today’s context. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarify this objective as it was not always clear what was meant by “dynamic capability”; - Set clear boundaries between this objective and Develop Agile Mindset; - Emphasize the need to remain robust and secure.

<p>Assess Risk and Technology Appetite</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessment is needed as appetite is essential for welcoming new digital technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Appetite for risk and technology has a greater or lesser role depending on what phase the DT is in; - Provide framing and understanding as to what DT encompasses; - Draw up proofs of concepts to assess risk.
<p>Sense Disruption and Change in the Market</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of the market and disruptions taking place is necessary; - Need to evolve whenever the market is evolving, or disruptions are taking place to stay relevant; - Critical input to the digital roadmap as it derives initiatives and determines refreshment of it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The openness of an organization enables it to sense more quickly; - This objective as a part of the assessment of the environment and the context (external view); - Set clear boundaries between this objective and Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies.
<p>Develop and Reconfigure Business and IT resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A dynamic and collaborative IT department is needed to develop and reconfigure business and IT resources; - It should be kept in mind continuously as strategy is subject to constant evolution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This objective needs further clarification; - Consider strategic alignment as a complementary objective as it was not clear that this objective also encompasses strategic alignment; - Determine what has to be done whenever current resources prove insufficient; - Assessment of capability and compatibility of IS determines whether this objective is necessary to elaborate upon.
<p>Seize Upon Trends and Emerging Technologies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The need of an organization to renew itself implies this objective; - Crucial to keep a watch on competition; - Successful if a close strategic fit is maintained thoroughly and accurately. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set clear boundaries between this objective and Sense Disruption and Change in the Market; - “When” an organization should consider this objective is crucial; - Must have close strategic fit as blindly imitating competitors will likely be unsuccessful; - This objective as a part of the assessment of the environment and the context (external view); - The velocity of new trends and emerging technologies coming up is sector-dependent.

Table C3: Main Findings Branch Two

Branch Two	Importance	Considerations to be made
Evaluate Financial Ability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Often underestimated in terms of time spent evaluating an organization’s financial ability; - The financial strength of an organization should be sufficient to support DT; - The financial aspect is both a driver and enabler for DT; - A business case should be made for DT projects; - Financial control is necessary to allocate more or fewer resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider not only the financial ability but also consider the ability and availability of people; - Consider the returns of DT; - Consider not only financial returns but also returns in terms of hours saved, in terms of efficiency; - Possible overlap between this objective and Identify <i>Possible Changes in Value Creation and Operational Efficiency.</i>

Table C4: Main Findings Branch Three

Branch Three	Importance	Considerations to be made
Identify Structural Changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of structural changes is necessary to support and enable DT; - Vital in order to steer the development of DT in the right direction; - DT is a structural change in itself; - Deploy the organizational structure as a means to achieve business objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The prioritization exercise concerning digital ideas includes identifying structural changes; - Importance varies according to the digital maturity assessment; - Connection with the operating model in place at an organization; - Determine nature of structural change (very disruptive or gradually); - Staff readiness is necessary to enable smooth structural changes; - Assessing digital maturity and defining the vision and strategic direction of a company allows an organization to be in a better position to identify structural changes; - Compatibility and interoperability of IS systems as a part of this objective; - Dynamic capability as a part of this objective.
Foster Digital Skillset and Mindset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Underlying pillar and strategic workforce for DT; - Crucial in terms of people’s ability to operate with digital technologies brought about by DT; - A proper digital mindset is necessary to enable DT; - Fostering digital skillset and an area of concern; - Inclusion of shop-floor level people is crucial; - Necessary to close the gap brought about by structural change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set-up trajectories to demonstrate the importance of DT and what is brought along by it; - Fostering a digital skillset and mindset is easier or more difficult according to the magnitude of an organization.

<p>Foster Transformational Leadership</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leadership in an organization has to lead by example; - Crucial for a leader to possess the desired mindset; otherwise, people are less likely to follow; - Digital initiatives fail due to a leadership deficit concerning DT; - Leadership drives an organization's vision and DT; - Solid support from the hierarchy is necessary for DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transformational leadership does not imply a smooth DT; a leader must possess the desired mindset regarding DT; - Showing commitment as a leader might be sufficient to motivate and push the people inside an organization; - The connection between this objective and <i>Define Strategic Vision and Direction.</i>
<p>Establish a DT Unit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A DT unit as a competency group or cross-functional department; - Proper governance of DT is imperative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance depends on corporate culture; - A separate unit potentially has detrimental effects on the motivation to carry through DT; - If an organization sets up a separate DT unit, it should be composed of function representatives that encourage and bring forth DT within their respective function, allowing a close fit between those who determine the DTS and those who carry it out, forming a cross- functional department or taskforce; - Responsibility regarding DT should not be taken away from those with operational roles; - DT units could exist at different levels within a company according to its magnitude, implying more DT units in some instances.

Table C5: Main Findings Branch Four

Branch Four	Importance	Considerations to be made
<p>Identify Possible Changes in Value Creation and Operational Efficiency</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value creation is the focus of the DTS; - Considering value creation is crucial for DT even to commence; - Operational efficiency and value creation contribute to the relevance of an organization among competitors; - Partly determines drivers of DT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value creation can be in terms of customer focus, product leadership, or operational excellence; - People within an organization should be open to DT to fulfill this objective; - Connection to an organization's financial ability; - Alignment with business strategy or strategies; - Value creation must shift in a favorable direction.
<p>Follow and Analyze Customer Behaviour</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Considerations must be made in the context of anticipating customer behavior; - Through a close relationship with customers, an organization can understand much better how to create value. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance depends on the type of DT, either being customer- centric or personnel-centric; - An organization should carefully approach the short-term character of customer thinking as an organization builds a DTS for the long term.

Identify Processes that can be Enhanced by Digital Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying these processes is crucial before introducing new digital technologies; - This identification is the focus of DT as it operationalizes the customer experience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible overlap with <i>Identify Possible Changes in Value Creation and Operational Efficiency</i>; - Consider the need to include “the bigger picture” to avoid tunnel-vision.
Establish Synergy between Digital and Traditional Offerings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing this synergy is imperative to move forward; - The synergy will enable the organization to identify much faster the processes that an organization should digitalize; - Optimization of business processes through synergy; - It is a necessity to analyze traditional set-ups and how digital technology can enhance these. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarify this objective as not only the offerings of an organization are considered here, also the set-ups within an organization; - Incorporate an objective regarding value creation by providing new types of services or creating an add-on to the business model fully through new technologies.

C.3 Shortcomings in General

Table C6 outlines the general shortcomings noted by interviewees. These shortcomings are categorized based on their nature. Weaknesses, shortcomings and proposals concerning a particular type of shortcoming are described in the column *Considerations to be made*. The latter could serve as an input for future developments.

Table C6: Shortcomings in General Outlined

Shortcomings in General	Considerations to be made
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Dependencies not always apparent as certain activities need to take place before embarking on other activities;</i> - <i>The need to clearly explain how the model is built up;</i> - <i>Develop and Assess Digital Maturity, Develop and Increase Dynamic Capability and Foster Digital Skillset and Mindset as an inside view representing the strengths and weaknesses of an organization;</i> - <i>Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies and Sense Disruption and Change in the Market as an outside view or strategic marketwatch representing the threats and opportunities for an organization;</i> - <i>The outside view or strategic marketwatch as a starting point.</i>
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>People aspect besides the financial aspect;</i> - <i>There should be a clear link to extant strategies within the organization as to envision alignment between them, leading to an integrated DTS;</i> - <i>More emphasis on change management, people, culture and governance;</i> - <i>Alignment with corporate transformation;</i> - <i>Include inspiration by external insights concerning DT through benchmarking with competitors and peers.</i>

<p>Practicality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of sequence or flow within the model; - Need of a starting point; - Describe the process on how to reiterate the model, how to follow it up, how to adjust, how to evaluate and test; - The model as a high-level checklist with key milestones specified for DT; - Define the necessary sub-actions an organization must take to achieve a particular objective, providing depth.
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Appendix D The Model as Reference

This part presents the answers to questions regarding the use of the model; would it be useful as documentation or as a guide, would it be convenient to use it to formulate a DTS, and is it realistic to use such a model.

– Useful as a Documentation or Guide

The responses to the first question were positive, although there were gradations in the answers. For example, Interviewee 4 saw the model’s potential and said he was convinced that the model could be helpful. Still, he pointed to the lack of flow: *“If you can build some kind of follow-up or flow into this, then you have an even more powerful model”*.

Interviewee 2 thought that the model could be helpful, but according to him, it is incomplete. It does lack practicality. He stated: *“It does have a large number of components that are already very insightful and relevant. (...) But should I be a business leader and I would only consider these components (...), and I think I have everything I need (...) then I think we effectively come to a chance of success of about 30% to 50%”*. He added that with a 50% chance of failure, people or organizations would not use the model. *“That 50% that would guarantee me success would still have to be added on to this slide”*. He further reasoned that this 50% was mainly in addition to Foster Transformational Leadership and Foster Digital Skillset and Mindset.

Interviewee 3 indicated that he thought the model was sound content-wise and from an academic perspective. However, he did state that strategy makers discuss other issues in practice and that the model lacks sequence. Interviewee 1 indicated that he thought that the model would be helpful. He reasoned that there are many exciting points present in the model, although other relevant objectives could undoubtedly be identified. He indicated: *“You cannot go to a company and say, this is how you do digital transformation now. I think this can be more of a checklist function at the beginning or the ending. Have we thought of everything?”* He went on to explain that he liked the word *“checklist”* when he looked at it. In contrast, he reasoned: *“You cannot hand this off to a CEO and then expect him to do it perfectly. You have to give [the model] to someone who is at home in project management and who does have experience in what this represents”*. To conclude this section, he stated that: *“Then*

when you start presenting this, many people are going to say, yes, yes, I know that, yes. *Digital Maturity*, I find that interesting. However, what it comprehends, that is often the next step, and you cannot understand that with this model”.

Interviewee 5 opined that this is “*definitely a guide*”. He further stated that with a reasonable explanation and a decent vision on paper, a first step could be taken towards using the model. Finally, he told this concerning the company in question: “*We are at least missing some things that we should do formally. So the model could definitely help with that, I believe*”.

– Ease of Use

When the interviewer asked the interviewees if the model would be easy to utilize, the answers were mainly suggestive. For example, Interviewee 4 indicated that he thought the model would be an excellent start. In doing so, he indicated that he did not know how in-depth the model would allow him to go. Then he suggested: “*For each objective, define a few more sub-actions of: how do we actually get to this objective?*” For example, he gave: “*How can I create an agile mindset?*” and “*How can I create a digital roadmap?*”

Also, he suggested creating, for example, a kind of guideline for each objective: “*For example, if you want to achieve this goal, these are a few standard actions that you can do to achieve this goal. So that you actually have a blueprint for achieving this goal*”. The interviewee further indicated that he saw “*some opportunities*”.

Interviewee 3 viewed the model as a checklist and suggested that organizations could use the model for this purpose. According to the interviewee, this would give a “*sense of comfort*” that strategy makers considered all relevant matters. Regarding the objectives included, he reasoned: “*It’s important to know that*”.

Interviewee 5 gave the following working method as a possible approach: “*So you are probably going to formulate something in [Microsoft] Word. You take those topics, and you start adding to them in your perspective. You have it evaluated by management, and they are going to evaluate and agree with it or not. Then you link several projects to it*”.

– Realistic to Deploy in Practice

When asked if it would be realistic to use this model in practice, responses indicated that it would not be sufficient. For example, Interviewee 3 reasoned that the model would not suffice for use in practice, however, he did indicate that the model could serve as a valuable input to establish a DT approach.

Interviewee 5 opined that strategy makers could use the model in practice with guidance or help. To this, he contributed that the author’s viewpoint could provide relief in this regard.

Interviewee 1 indicated that it would be realistic to use such a model in consultancy. But he reflected that: “*For people who are not at home with this, they are going to miss a certain depth in here*”.

Appendix E Details on the Adapted Model

E.1 Added Objectives

- *Analyze Organizational Context and Environment*
This objective represents the outside view. Both *Seize upon Trends and Emerging Technologies* and *Sense Disruption and Change in the Market* form the sub-objectives. This objective is added to distinguish the inside view from the outside view clearly.
- *Assess Capability and Compatibility of Infrastructure*
Assessing capability and compatibility refer to the infrastructure in place within an organization. It is added as a sub-objective of Develop and Reconfigure Business and IT Resources as assessing the capability and compatibility of infrastructure partly determines the need to develop further and reconfigure business and IT resources. The distinction between infrastructure and IT departments is made to avoid confusion.
- *Assess Capability and Compatibility of IT Departments*
The assessment of the capability and compatibility of IT departments is needed to identify the need to develop further and reconfigure business and IT resources. The distinction in the model is made to avoid confusion between infrastructure and IT departments.
- *Develop and Assess Strategic Alignment*
The need to strategically align with other business strategies and corporate strategy is necessary to ensure an integrated DTS.
- *Evaluate and Increase People Ability*
This objective refers to people’s ability within an organization to close the gap made by the identified structural changes. An organization should evaluate and increase people’s ability to enable smooth structural changes such as organizational change. *Foster Transformational Leadership* and *Foster Digital Skillset and Mindset* have been included as sub-objectives.
- *Identify New Methods of Value Creation*
This objective regards the identification of value creation by providing new types of services or creating an add-on to the business model entirely through digital technologies.

E.2 Modified Objectives

- *Establish a DT Entity*
“Unit” is replaced by “Entity” to highlight integration instead of an entirely separate department. This DT entity should be composed of function representatives that encourage and bring forth DT within their respective functions, allowing a close fit between those who determine the DTS and

those who carry it out, forming a cross-functional department. Consequently, this objective aims at bottom-up support from the lower hierarchy levels of the organization.

- *Establish Synergy between D & T Processes and Offerings*

The word “processes” is included in this objective to encompass the necessary synergy between digital and traditional processes. Thus, it implies the synergy between traditional and digital offerings and the synergy between traditional and digital business processes.

Chapter 6

**On the ability of novice modelers to identify,
represent and trace tactical and strategic
conceptual elements in business process and
enterprise modeling**

Appendix A: search strings

Database	Search string	Search parameters	Hits
Google scholar	("Cognitive style") ("strategic" OR "strategy" OR "goal based") ("business process model") ("Quality" OR "completeness" OR "complexity")	any time, sort by relevance, English pages only	54
Google scholar	("Cognitive style") ("modelers" OR "modeler")	any time, sort by relevance, English pages only	465
Google scholar	allintitle:(cognitive) ("model" OR "modelling" OR "modeller" OR "modeler" OR "modeller's" OR "modeler's") ("quality")	any time, sort by relevance, English pages only, title only	77
Google scholar	allintitle:(business process model" "business process modelling" OR "conceptual model" OR "conceptual modelling") ("quality")	any time, sort by relevance, English pages only, title only	1
Google scholar	"business process model" AND "cognitive style" AND ("strateg" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand" OR "completeness" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	any time, sort by relevance, English pages only, title only	70
IEEEExplore	"business process model" AND "quality" AND "cognitive"	standard	9
IEEEExplore	"process model" AND "quality" AND "cognitive"	standard	1
IEEEExplore	"business process model" AND "quality" AND "cognitive" AND "strategic"	standard	0
IEEEExplore	"business process model" AND "cognitive"	standard	7
IEEEExplore	"process model" AND "cognitive"	standard	122
IEEEExplore	"process model" AND "cognitive" AND "strateg*" ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "complex")	standard	4
IEEEExplore	"process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	standard	3
Springerlink	"process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	standard	19491

Springerlink	"business process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	standard	1369
Springerlink	"business process model" AND "cognitive style" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	standard	41
Springerlink	"business process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	standard	1370
Springerlink	("business process model" OR "process model") AND ("cognitive style" OR "overload" OR "cognitive fit" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "correctness" "traceab*" OR "readability" OR "metrics" OR "correctness"))	standard	2263
Springerlink	"process model" AND "cognitive style" AND "quality"	standard	528
Springerlink	"process model" AND "cognitive style" AND "quality" AND "strategic"	standard	230
Sciadirect	"business process model" AND "cognitive style" AND ("strateg" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand" OR "completeness" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	wildcards not supported and only 8 boolean terms allowed	7
Sciadirect	"process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("strateg" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand" OR "completeness" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	wildcards not supported and only 8 boolean terms allowed	11935
Sciadirect	"process model" AND "cognitive" AND ("quality" OR "understand" OR "completeness" OR "traceability" OR "correctness")	wildcards not supported and only 8 boolean terms allowed	96
ACM digital library	("business process model" OR "process model") AND ("cognitive style" OR "overload" OR "cognitive fit" AND ("strateg*" OR "goal") AND ("quality" OR "understand*" OR "eval" OR "completeness" OR "comprehens*" OR "correctness" "traceab*" OR "readability" OR "metrics" OR "correctness"))	standard	14949
ACM digital library	[All: "business process model"] AND [All: "cognitive"] AND [[All: "strateg*"] OR [All: "goal"]] AND [[All: "quality"] OR [All: "understand*"]] OR [All: "eval"] OR [All:	standard	46

	"completeness"] OR [All: "comprehens*"] OR [All: "traceability"] OR [All: "correctness"]]		
ACM digital library	"process model" AND "cognitive style" AND "quality" AND "strategic"	standard	7
ACM digital library	"process model" AND "cognitive style" AND "quality"	standard	19
ACM digital library	[All: "process model"] AND [All: "cognitive"] AND [[All: "strateg*"] OR [All: "goal"]] AND [[All: "quality"] OR [All: "understand*"] OR [All: "eval"] OR [All: "completeness"] OR [All: "comprehens*"] OR [All: "traceability"] OR [All: "correctness"]]	standard	609

Appendix B: variables

All likert scale questions were on a scale from 1 to 5. (1 = Not at all, 2 = Slightly, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Very, 5 = Extremely)

name	respondents name
student_number	respondents student number
occupation	What is your primary occupation?
edu	What is your educational background (highest previous degree)?
age	How old are you?
gender	male or female
fam_UML	How familiar are you with the Unified Modelling Language (UML)?
fam_BMRUP	How familiar are you with the Business Modelling Discipline of the Rational Unified Process?
fam_BUCM	How familiar are you with the Business Use-Case Model?
clarity_BO	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Business Objective)
clarity_BG	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Business Goal)
clarity_BUC	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Business Use-Case)
clarity_BA	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Business Actor)
clarity_BW	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Business Worker)
clarity_association	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Association Link)
clarity_dependency	To what extent are the following concepts clear to you? (Dependency Link)
clarity_example	To what extent is the example clear to you?
case_instructions	To what extent were the instructions clear to you?
case_description	To what extent is the description of the TransLogistic clear to you?
ease_BO	How easy was it to model following components? (Business objective(s))
ease_BG	How easy was it to model following components? (Business Goals(s))
ease_BUC	How easy was it to model following components? (Business Use-Case(s))
ease_BUCtoBG	How easy was it to model following components? (Linking Use-Case(s) to Business Goal(s))
ease_BA	How easy was it to model following components? (Business Actor(s))
ease_BW	How easy was it to model following components? (Business Worker(s))
ease_relationships	How easy was it to model following components? (Identify relationships between components)
method_useful	I find this method useful.
method_understandable	The method is clear and understandable to me.
method_futurejob	I would find the method useful in my (future) job.
method_skilful	It would be easy for me to become skilful at using this method.
method_enhance	I believe that the method enhances the business modelling discipline of RUP.
method_easy	I find the method easy to use.
method_use	I would use the method during the process of software development or business process engineering.
BO_identification	BO identification on 1
BG_identification	BG identification on 1
BOBG2_identification	BO/BG2 identification on 1
BUC_identification	BUC identification on 1
BUClinkstoBG	BUC links to BG on 1
BABW_identification	BA/BW identification on 1
Links_illegal	Illegal links present in model on 1

Expert_review	Expert review score on 10
Quality_score	Weighted quality score on 10
Pass	Pass
CSI_score	respondents cognitive style index score on 76
CSI_cats5	CSI 5 categories
CSI_cats3	CSI 3 categories
CSI_cats2	CSI 2 categories
BO_desc	BO identification
BG_desc	BG identification
BOBG2_desc	BO/BG2 identification
BUC_desc	BUC identification
BUClinkstobg_desc	BUC links to BG
BABW_desc	BA/BW identification
Linksillegal_desc	Illegal links present in model
fam_modelling_factor	familiarity with modelling factor
clarity_theory_factor	clarity of theory factor
ease_case_factor	ease of modelling case factor
usefulness_BUCM_factor	usefulness of the BUCM factor
ease_BUCM_factor	ease of modelling the BUCM factor

Appendix C: Experiment

First name	
Last name	
Student number	

Experiment: Modelling Strategic Elements

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this explorative experiment about the impact of cognitive style on the ability to model strategic elements. This experiment consist of four main parts to be completed chronologically.

The experiment starts with a questionnaire in order to measure your cognitive style. In the following part 1, you will be asked about your background. In part 2, theory concerning modelling strategic elements will be provided and your understanding about this theory will be surveyed. The summary of all elements (modelling constructs and links/relationships) that are needed including a basic example can be used as a reference when modelling.

The third part is made up of a case in which you will be asked to identify and model the strategic and tactical elements of the organisation's business processes, using the Business Use-Case Model (BUCM). You need to model these elements on the basis of an available textual description. Finally, your perceived difficulty to do this will be examined as well.

The collected data from this experiment will be confidential. However, by completing this experiment in a satisfactory manner you could earn a maximum of 1.5 bonus points for your Business Process Management and Integrated Software Systems course. For this reason, we require you to fill in your name and student number above.

We appreciate your honesty and willingness to assist in this research.

Part 1: Background

1. What is your primary occupation?

- Student
- Researcher
- Business Analyst
- Software Developer
- Other (please precise):

2. What is your educational background (highest previous degree)?

- High School
- Bachelor (please precise):
- Master (please precise):
- PhD (please precise):

3. How old are you?

4. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

1. How familiar are you with the *Unified Modelling Language (UML)*?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
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2. How familiar are you with the *Business Modelling Discipline of the Rational Unified Process*?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

3. How familiar are you with the *Business Use-Case Model*?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

Part 2: Theory

Modelling constructs of the RUP/UML Business Use-Case Model

To model the strategic and tactical level, several modelling constructs can be used, interconnected with links/relationships. Some of these constructs are described below, together with examples and a visual representation.

The Business Use-Case Model is a model of the business goals (strategic level) and intended functions (tactical level). The business supports many goals directly, by having business use cases that achieve one or more goals. However, it is not invalid to have goals that are not supported by use cases, as these often indicate goals that are affected by environmental factors. Creating a BUCM can be done with following steps:

Step 1: Identify the Business Objective(s) and Business Goal(s)

A Business Goal is a requirement that the business must satisfy. They represent the strategic level and their purpose is to translate the business strategy into measurable steps. A Business Objective is a high-level Business Goal, which is more abstract. The main difference is that there can be a metric associated with the goal, for which the objective is too abstract.

E.g. *Sustainable Growth* is a Business Objective as it's part of the strategy and as it is abstract. E.g. *Increase Market Share* is a Business Goal as it's a measurable step to obtain sustainable growth.

Step 2: Identify the Business Use-Cases (and which Business Goal they support)

A Business Use-Case defines a set of business use-case instances, where each instance is a sequence of actions that a business performs in order to yield value to a particular Business Actor. A Business Use-Case is an abstract element that describes a business process from an external, value-added point of view. They are business processes that cut across organisation boundaries.

E.g. *Manage Sales Goods Return* is a business use-case, because it is a sequence of actions (receive the request for return from the client, receive returned goods, reimburse client, ...) and thus a business process. This business process cuts across the organisation boundaries as it involves client service, logistics, ...

E.g. *Manage Sales Goods Return* is a business use-case that supports the business goal *Easy Delivery and Return of Goods* which is a refinement of the business objective *Customer Satisfaction*

Step 3: Identify the Business Actor instances

A Business Actor is someone or something outside of the business, that interacts with the business. As they are OUTSIDE of the scope of the business, they only have an understanding of the externally visible behaviour of the business.

E.g. A *Client* is a Business Actor as it interacts with the business by buying goods or calling the client service for example, but he is outside of the scope of the business. He doesn't know details about what specifically happens inside the organisation.

Step 4: Identify the Business Worker instances

A *Business Worker* is a role or a set of roles that a human or software system plays **INSIDE** the organisation.

E.g. An *Operator* is a Business Worker that manipulates machines inside an organisation. He knows how (part of) the organisation works in detail.

Step 5: Identify the relationships between the different components

- An *Association* is a relationship between two elements.

- A *Dependency* is a relationship between two elements, where one element depends on the other.
 - *Supports* denotes the business goal(s) for which a business use-case provides support. A business goal should support one or more such goals.

Business Goals can be linked to each other or to Business Use-Case elements of the BUCM with a Dependency Link. A Business Goal refines a Business Objective, while a BUC supports a goal. The BUC can only be linked with the goals, as the objectives are too abstract.

Business Use-Cases can be associated with Business Actors and Business Workers. They can be connected with an Association Relationship.

Step 6: Bring everything together in a diagram

An Example: Knitting Shop

A small knitting shop wants to ensure customer satisfaction by providing good products and by providing additional services. Customers can buy wool and cotton of different colours and sizes. These are provided by an eco-labelled supplier. The shop owner proposes knitting courses as an additional service every Wednesday and Saturday.

Step 1: Identify the Business Objective(s) and Business Goal(s)

- Business Objective: 'ensure customer satisfaction'
- Business Goal 1: 'provide good products'
- Business Goal 2: 'provide additional services'

Step 2: Identify the Business Use-Cases (and which Business Goal they support)

- Business Use-Case 1: 'sell products' (supports Business Goal 1)
- Business Use-Case 2: 'buy eco-labelled products' (supports Business Goal 1)
- Business Use-Case 3: 'offer knitting courses' (supports Business Goal 2)

Step 3: Identify the Business Actor(s)

- Business Actor 1: 'customer'
- Business Actor 2: 'supplier'

Step 4: Identify the Business Worker(s)

- Business Worker 1: 'shop owner'

Step 5: Identify the relationships between the different components

- Business Goal 1 and 2 refine the Business Objective
- Business Actor 1 is associated with Business Use-Case 1 and 3
- Business Actor 2 is associated with Business Use-Case 2
- Business Worker 1 is associated with Business Use-Case 1, 2 and 3

Step 6: Bring everything together in a diagram

(note that you do not have to use <<refine>> or <<support>> for clarity purposes)

Questionnaire: Comprehension of the concepts

To what extent are the following *concepts* clear to you?

(1 = Not at all, 2 = Slightly, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Very, 5 = Extremely)

Business Objective	1	2	3	4	5
Business Goal	1	2	3	4	5
Business Use-Case	1	2	3	4	5
Business Actor	1	2	3	4	5
Business Worker	1	2	3	4	5
Association Link	1	2	3	4	5
Dependency Link	1	2	3	4	5

To what extent is the *example* clear to you?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

Part 3: TransLogistic Case

Introduction: You're hired as a business analyst working for a consultancy firm. You are currently working on a project, for which you're asked to model the strategic and tactical elements of the organisation's business processes on the basis of the following textual description. You need to model these levels using the Business Use-Case Model (BUCM). A summary of all elements (modelling constructs and links/relationships) that are needed is provided for you to use as a reference when modelling (see part 2).

Note: Only take into consideration the information that is given in the description.

TransLogistic is a software company wanting to develop information systems supporting modern supply chains. This involves a series of actors incarnated by various collaborating or competing companies where several roles played by lots of individuals are interacting to achieve common as well as individual goals. The ordered products need to be shipped from a vendor to a buyer or recipient, using several transport modes (by truck, railways, boat and plane), controlled by several international actors (shippers, final clients (business actor), carriers and infrastructure managers (business workers), governmental agencies (e.g. railways, harbours, etc.). Collaboration between these actors is required to integrate transportation modes and schedules to achieve a smooth logistic flow.

The goal of the project is to develop a single platform allowing these actors to share information and collaborate on a global basis. This would lead to optimizing the whole of the processes on a global basis. In particular, the project involves several partners such as university researchers, Belgian governmental agencies and private companies from the logistics and IT sector. As a result, the software solution needs to be able to „communicate“ with the existing software systems of the involved parties (actors).

Outbound logistics (OL) is the part of the supply chain which focused on the product delivery with consequently a strong highlight on stocking and transportation. The development of a collaborative platform or system for OL actors is highly complex and thus implies the necessity of a systematic Software Engineering (SE) approach presenting various levels of knowledge and views to: furnish adequate documentation to each stakeholder, allow iterative planning, cover all of the traditional software development disciplines, be integrated in a mature development life cycle, ensure adaptability and flexibility as well as envisage third party software data reuse.

The analysis of the socio-economic context in which the project takes place has led to various concrete objectives. Firstly, the development of control systems tailored to the rail freight expectations. Next, the development of real time innovative localizing solutions covering the whole OL chain based on a new generation of positioning systems as well as on the optimal and extended use of existing infrastructures. Finally, the development of an online collaborative logistic platform allowing the major OL actors to share information for a better optimization of the logistic chain.

The final client orders a shipment from a supplier, who will have to deliver this order. The shipper's expedition representative will treat orders. He will plan the forthcoming/required material flows by building Logistic Requests on the basis of the customers' orders. The final client generally has little impact on strategic OL decisions.

The shipper's expedition representative will treat expeditions by building transportation calls on the available logistic requests. The shipper will turn towards one or several carriers to realize that shipment.

The carrier receives transportation orders from shippers for the realization of shipments to final clients. The carrier's order representative plans logistic requests. He evaluates the possibilities (eventually by relaxing certain constraints) of accepting the transmitted transportation calls. The carriers' planner manages the services. He has to update the carriers' transportation offer in function of the general environment (demand and capacity on particular origins and destinations, new transportation possibilities, etc.).

The carriers' scheduler manages the transports by planning the carriers' (physical) transports linked to its transportation offer to answer to the accepted transportation calls demand.

The managing of resources is done by the infrastructure manager. He ensures an adequate planning of the required resources (working teams, docks, cranes, etc.) for the planned transports. The utilization of the infrastructure is rented to the carriers while other services could be offered (storage, cross-docking, etc.). The infrastructure manager is involved in the evaluation of the capacity he plans to offer to the carriers as well as the policies for allowing them on their infrastructure. He also receives an infrastructure load from the carriers and schedule their operations and teams to meet such load. When communication is absent, infeasibilities generally result in delays.

The transport management system tracks transported goods through real-time track and performs a series of activities such as dynamic replenishments, alternative route calculation, etc.

Managing the fleet is done by the fleet management system. It accomplishes a series of specific tasks in the management of a carrier vehicle fleet as for example telematics (tracking and diagnostics), driver management, fuel management, vehicle maintenance and so on.

The warehouse management system manages the warehouse by managing the movement and storage of materials within the warehouse and processing the associated transactions, such as shipping, receiving, stocking and picking.

The enterprise resource planning (ERP) takes care of transferring orders. It manages all the input data flows that must be transferred from the ERP system or to the actor ERP system.

Step 1: Identify the Business Objective(s) and Business Goal(s) from the point of view from TransLogistic

Step 1b: Identify at least 2 business objectives and or goals which are not explicitly stated in the text, but are relevant in the context of the case (also include these in the drawing of your model in step 6)

Step 2 : Identify the Business Use-Cases (and which Business Goal they support)

Step 3 : Identify the Business Worker(s)

Step 4 : Identify the Business Actor(s)

Step 5 : Identify the relationships between the different components

Step 6: Bring everything together

(Draw a complete model based on your solutions for previous steps, note that you do not have to use <<refine>> or <<support>> for clarity purposes)

Questionnaire: How did you perceive the case?

To what extent were the *instructions* clear to you?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

To what extent is the *description of the TransLogistic* clear to you?

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

How easy was it to *model following components*?

(1 = Not at all, 2 = Slightly, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Very, 5 = Extremely)

Business Objective(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Business Goal(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Business Use-Case(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Linking Use-Case(s) to Business Goal(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Business Actor(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Business Worker(s)	1	2	3	4	5
Identify relationships between components	1	2	3	4	5

To what extent do the following sentences relate to you?

1. I find this method useful.

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

2. The method is clear and understandable to me.

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

3. **I would find the method useful in my (future) job.**

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

4. **It would be easy for me to become skilful at using this method.**

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

5. **I believe that the method enhances the business modelling discipline of RUP.**

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

6. **I find the method easy to use.**

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

7. **I would use the method during the process of software development or business process engineering.**

Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
------------	----------	------------	------	-----------

If you have anything you want to add (comments, additional information, etc.) please do so:

Scrap page

Appendix D: reference model

Part 3: TransLogistic Case

Note: Only take into consideration the information that is given in the description. What is not given in the description should not be modelled.

Note: You will be asked to make a drawing of the model, in case you made a mistake, you can just cross it out and redo that part.

Your solution should be drawn on the empty pages attached. Please indicate which diagrams are part of the final solution and cross out any scrap pages.

TransLogistic is a ^{software} shipping company ~~with~~ a modern supply chain, involving a series of actors incarnated by various collaborating or competing companies where several roles played by lots of individuals are interacting to achieve common as well as individual goals. The ordered products need to be shipped from a vendor to a buyer or recipient, using several transport modes (by truck, railways, boat, plane), controlled by several international actors (shippers, final clients (business actor), carriers and infrastructure managers (business workers), governmental agencies (e.g. railways, harbors, etc. ^{ok})). Collaboration between these actors is required to integrate transportation modes and schedules to achieve a smooth logistic flow. ^{making to develop information systems supporting}

The goal of the project is to develop a single platform allowing these actors to share information and collaborate on a global basis. This would lead to optimizing the whole of the processes on a global basis. In particular, the project involves several partners such as university researchers, Belgian governmental agencies and private companies from the logistics and IT sector. As a result, the software solution needs to be able to „communicate“ with the existing software systems of the involved parties (actors).

Outbound logistics (OL) is the part of the supply chain which focused on the product delivery with consequently a strong highlight on stocking and transportation. The development of a collaborative platform or system for OL actors is highly complex and thus implies the necessity of a systematic Software Engineering (SE) approach presenting various levels of knowledge and views to: furnish adequate documentation to each stakeholder, allow iterative planning, cover all of the traditional software development disciplines, be integrated in a mature development life cycle, ensure adaptability and flexibility as well as envisage third party software data reuse.

The analysis of the socio-economic context in which the project takes place has led to various concrete objectives. Firstly, the development of control systems tailored to the rail freight expectations. Next, the development of real time innovative localizing solutions covering the whole OL chain based on a new generation of positioning systems as well as on the optimal and extended use of existing infrastructures. Finally, the development of an online collaborative logistic platform allowing the major OL actors to share information for a better optimization of the logistic chain.

constraints, pickup and delivery dates as well as transportation mode. The shipper's expedition representative will treat expeditions by building transportation calls on the available logistic requests. The shipper will turn towards one or several carriers to realize that shipment. The carrier owns the transportation capacity. It receives transportation orders from shippers for the realization of shipments to final clients. ~~These final clients are generally not involved in the choice of the carrier.~~ The carrier's order representative plans logistic requests. He evaluates the possibilities (eventually by relaxing certain constraints) of accepting the transmitted transportation calls. The carriers' planner manages the services. He has to update the carriers' transportation offer in function of the general environment (demand and capacity on particular origins and destinations, new transportation possibilities, etc.). The carriers' scheduler manages the transports by planning the carriers' (physical) transports linked to its transportation offer to answer to the accepted transportation calls demand. The managing of resources is done by the infrastructure manager. He ensures an adequate planning of the required resources (working teams, docks, cranes, etc.) for the planned transports. The utilization of the infrastructure is rented to the carriers while other services could be offered (storage, cross-docking, etc.). The infrastructure manager is involved in the evaluation of the capacity he plans to offer to the carriers as well as the policies for allowing them on their infrastructure. He also receives an infrastructure load from the carriers and schedule their operations and teams to meet such load. When communication is absent, infeasibilities generally result in delays. The transport management system tracks transported goods through real-time track and performs a series of activities such as dynamic replenishments, alternative route calculation, etc. Managing the fleet is done by the fleet management system. It accomplishes a series of specific tasks in the management of a carrier vehicle fleet as for example telematics (tracking and diagnostics), driver management, fuel management, vehicle maintenance and so on. The warehouse management system manages the warehouse by managing the movement and storage of materials within the warehouse and processing the associated transactions, such as shipping, receiving, stocking and picking. The enterprise resource planning (ERP) takes care of transferring orders. It manages all the input data flows that must be transferred from the ERP system or to the actor ERP system.

Step 1: Identify the Business Objective(s) and Business Goal(s)

From the point of view of Translogistic.

- BO1: Optimize the ~~supply~~ chain globally through IT
↑
quantitative
- BO2: Support and generate profit from all supported actors
- BG1: Optimal integration of the platform with existing systems
- BG2: Furnish adequate data, information and data to involved actors.

- B&3: Develop ~~in~~ through iterative cycles.
- B&4: Reuse relevant off the shelf services.
- B&5: Support regulation of transport (including rail, road, ...)
- B&6: Support multi-modal real time positioning
- B&7: Support cooperation between OL actors without confidential information transmission.

Step 2 : Identify the Business Use-Cases (and which Business Goal they support)

- BUC 1: Treat Orders
- ~~BUC 2: Ship/Transport products~~
- BUC 2: Treat Expeditions
- BUC 3: Plan Logistic Requests
- BUC 4: Manage Transports
- BUC 5: Manage Resources
- BUC 6: Track Transports
- (BUC 7: Manage Fleet)
- (BUC 8: Manage Warehouse)
- (BUC 9: Transfer Order)

Step 3 : Identify the Business Actors

- ~~BUA 1: Expedition Representative~~ BUC 1 ~~BUC 2~~
- ~~BUA 2: C. order Representative~~ BUC 3
- ~~BUA 3: C scheduler~~ BUC 4
- ~~BUA 4: Infrastructure Manager~~ BUC 5
- ~~Act 5: TMS~~ BUC 6
- ~~Act 6: FMS~~ BUC 7
- ~~Act 7: WMS~~

Step 4 : Identify the Business Actors

- ~~Act 5: TMS~~
- BA 1: TMS BUC 6
- BA 2: FMS BUC 7
- BA 3: WMS BUC 8
- BA 4: ERP BUC 9

Step 5 : Identify the relationships between the different components

